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English Emotional Signification in Pragmatic Communication

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摘要

一个话语中“语言情感”与“韵律情感”以及“面部情感”是否能够匹配是一种具有挑战性的语用交际行为，它会影响到对话者在意义、功能和意图方面的理解。在语言学中，研究话语中并非仅通过语义语言表层结构来表现的意义、功能和意图，属于符号学和语用学范畴。这篇论文中提到的由面部表情和语调情感对话语语言内容产生影响，从而导致意义、功能和意图发生变化的现象被称为“情感符号化”，它是符号学和语用学的高度关注点。在符号学中，任何具有意义的东西都被看作是一个符号，并且它具有一个指代对象。符号的指代对象可能会因符号的修改而发生变化。情感符号化的过程会影响话语作为符号的指代对象。当一句话接受了与主要命题内容相关的修改，例如通过语调情感的修改而不是语言修改时，它的指代对象就会发生变化。在语用学中，当话语受到上下文、心理状态和相邻语音或文本等因素的影响时，它可能会改变含义。虽然有证据表明，在将同一话语用于表示不同态度和意图（如兴奋、能量、持续时间和响度）时，调式生理特征的声学可检测性成为了韵律研究的证据，但对话语中的情感面部表情、韵律情感和语言内容如何导致情感符号化仍存在不充分的方法，特别是因为韵律分析工具无法检测多模态话语意图而不仅仅是调式意图。因为情感并非是声音，声音也不是情感，虽然它们都可以用于强化话语的含义和意图，并在声学分析工具中以不同的方式被检测出来。因此，本论文的目标有两个。第一个是为研究面部表情、声音和话语的相互作用和不匹配中出现的语用含义、功能和意图建立基础。第二个是找到支持在对话中面部表情、声音和话语的相互作用和不匹配中存在的语用含义、功能和意图的证据。为了研究情感符号化所导致的语义、功能和意图变化的本质，本研究进行了两个音韵学实验。第一项实验旨在确定在八种不同情感表达中以英语发出的话语声学上的差异，并找到平均振幅差异。在 Praat 语音分析软件的帮助下，本实验使用预先构建的含有十个英语话语的录音，每个话语由十个不同的说话者用八种不同的情感表达，并进行了录制和分析。因此，研究假设情感作为话语意义的载体，除非有理论解释情感的面部表情和韵律如何导致不同类型的话语具有不同的含义、功能和意图，否则情感无法表达话语的可测量的和声学可探测的意图。为了验证这一假设，在音韵学实验后还进行了额外的话语意图听者判断实验。该实验使用匹配和不匹配的情感言语行为作为对话的回应，并考虑到本研究理论基础部分提供的解释，即并非所有类型的

句子或 塞尔语言行为类别在受到情感标志影响时都会具有相似的话语功能和意图。是的，第一个实验的结果证实了在不同情感类别下发出的话语，其情感表达在声学上是可以被检测到的。第二个音韵实验旨在确定被假定为具有特定功能和意图的不同情感类别的言语/话语是否可以被英语听众理解。在这个实验中，英语听众通过在每段对话中从四个选项中选择说话者所表达的意图，来回答附带英语对话的多项选择调查问题。第二个实验的结果表明，同一个言语行为在不同情感声调下的表达，会被英语听众解释为具有不同的意图。然而，在一个表达情感的言语中，情感类别和言语意图之间并没有一对一的关系。差异是由于言语本身的情感基础、言语中所传递的内容以及用于表示言语的新情感力量的情感类别的自然属性引起的。因此，本研究通过专注于“情感符号化”概念，采用两个理论基础——情感符号化作为符号过程以及情感符号化作为语用行为，以及两种研究方法——两个语音学实验和关于言语意图听众判断的一项语言学调查，成功地描述了一种理解言语含义、功能和意图的方法。该方法基于情感面部表情、声音情感和言语语言内容在交互中的匹配和不匹配，通过情感符号化的过程进行解释。两个实验收集到的证据均支持以下结论：在八种情感表达中，一个言语中所包含的情感类别会导致不同的声学特征；同时，在八种情感表达中，人类可以感知到不同的言语情感意图。这一结论得到了第一个实验中言语情感类别的平均振幅和第二个实验中言语情感意图的证据支持。这些证据最终表明，不同的声学特征和意图可以分别表达不同的意义、功能和意图。

关键词：情感意义、语用意义、符号过程、言语行为、语用行为。

ABSTRACT

The matching and mismatching of ‘linguistic emotion’ with ‘prosodic emotion’ and ‘facial emotion’ of an utterance is a challenging pragmatic communication behavior, and it affects interlocutors’ meanings, functions, and intentions. In linguistics, meanings, functions, and intentions of an utterance which are not primarily present in only semantic linguistic surface structure of an utterance are studied in semiotics and pragmatics. The change in meaning, function, and intention due to influence of facial expressions and prosodic emotions to an utterance linguistic content has been referred to as ‘Emotional signification’ in this thesis and is of high concern to both semiotics and pragmatics. In semiotics, anything which has meaning is regarded as a semiotic sign and it has a reference. The reference of a semiotic sign may change based on modification of a sign. The process of Emotional signification affects the reference of an utterance as a semiotic sign. When an utterance receives modifications that are associated with the main propositional contents such as prosodic emotional modification without linguistic modifications it changes its reference. In Pragmatics, an utterance may change meaning when it is affected by factors such as context, mental states, and neighboring speech or text. Although there is evidence from prosody studies about acoustic detectability of prosodic physiological features manifesting when the same utterance is spoken to indicate different attitude and intentions such as excitation, energy, duration, and loudness, there are still inadequate approaches to how emotional facial expressions, prosodic emotions, and linguistic content of an utterance cause emotional signification, especially given the inability of intonation analysis tools to detect multi-modal utterance intention rather than intonational intentions since emotions are not sounds and sounds are not emotions even though they can both be used to conditions different utterance meanings and intentions, and can both still be detected differently in acoustic analysis tools. For this reason, this thesis covers two aims, which are, first, laying down foundations to studying pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and utterance. Second, finding evidence supporting presence of pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of a face, voice, and an utterance in interlocution. Thus, to investigate the essence of changes in meanings, functions, and intentions due to emotional signification, two phonetics experiments have been applied. The first experiment was designed to find out acoustic differences in an English utterance when spoken in eight different emotional expressions and found mean amplitudes

differences. With the aid of Praat speech analysis software, the ready constructed ten English utterances which were spoken by ten different speakers each in eight different emotional expressions were recorded for experiment analysis. It was then hypothesized that, since emotions as carriers of utterance meanings may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intention of an utterance unless there are theoretical explanations of how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions, there was therefore an additional utterance intention listener judgement experiment which used matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses to dialogues formulated by consulting explanations laid in the theoretical foundation part that not all types of sentence and or classes of Searle speech acts react similarly in terms of utterance function and intention when affected by emotional signification. The results of the first experiment confirm that one utterance when spoken with different emotion categories, such emotional manifestations are acoustically detectable.

The second phonetic experiment was designed to determine whether different emotional categories of one speech/utterance presupposed to have specific functions and intentions could be physically comprehended by English listeners. In this experiment English listeners responded to multiple choice survey questions attached with English dialogues by selecting the speaker's signified intention from four options from each dialogue. The results of the second experiment indicate that one speech act utterance when spoken with different emotional voices, its emotional manifestation is interpreted by English listeners as capable of carrying different intentions. However, there is no one to one relationship between emotion category and utterance intention in a signified emotional utterance. The differences happen because of the baseline emotional nature of an utterance, the nature of an utterance propositional content, and emotional category of a newer emotive force used in signifying an utterance. Therefore, this research has managed to describe an approach to understanding utterance meanings, functions, and intentions which are present in matches and mismatches of emotional facial expressions, voice emotions and utterance linguistic content during interlocution by focusing on the concept 'emotional signification' using two theoretical foundations which are, Emotional signification as a semiotic process, and emotional signification as a pragmatic act, and two research methods which are two phonetics experiments one linguistic survey about Utterance intention listener judgement. The evidence collected from results of the two experiments which are mean amplitudes of utterances emotion categories in experiment one and utterance emotional intentions in experiment two,

support presence of acoustic differences in an utterance spoken in eight emotional expressions and human perceivable distinctive utterance emotional intentions in eight emotional expressions. Such evidence is conclusively presented to be aligning with accounts laid down as capable of carrying different meanings, functions, and intentions.

Key Words: Emotional signification, Pragmatic meaning, Semiotic process, Speech act, Pragmatic act.

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CHAPTER ONE INTRODUCTION

1.1 Research Background.

The idea onto starting this research came from curious experience in observing pragmatic facial expressions of English emotional utterances and their implications in pragmatic communication where I observed use of misunderstood and often misinterpreted emotional facial expressions accompanying English emotional utterances in English language conversations. English emotional utterances when accompanied with opposite or different facial expressions and prosodic/voice emotions often tend to mislead interlocutors' perceptions of utterances due to presence of expected specific emotional utterances meanings, functions, and intentions and thus posing challenge and difficulties in communication.

The problem of this research may be pragmatically seen in the way speakers converse their emotions. This problem may be built on three aspects.

A. The overt aspect of the problem.

- (Observable pragmatic incompetence, i.e., misrepresentation and misinterpretation of emotional facial expressions and utterances).

B. The covert aspect of the problem.

- (Unobservable neuroscience performance on production and comprehension of emotional facial expressions and their linguistic interpretation).

C. The root aspect/ The root of the problem.

- (The semiotic and cultural sources shaping the problem).

Challenges emerge in noticing and interpreting functions and intentions of English emotional utterances and facial expressions where use of facial expression to an often-heard utterance, "*I am so happy to meet you*" may simply be pragmatically misunderstood based on facial expression accompanying it. So, the challenge appears to be the misunderstood myriad pragmatic facial expressions where an expression such as '*I'm so sorry my dear!*' is expressed with different facial expressions such as 'the sad face, angry face,

happy face, amazed face, serious face, or disgust face' regardless of the expected English language pragmatic emotional facial response.

Another example is a spoken utterance such as *'If I were you, I'd leave him straight away'* which appears to have different meanings based on its accompanied emotional signification. For instance, with a negative emotional facial expression it may be interpreted as a warning, with a positive emotional facial expression it may be interpreted as a wish, with a neutral emotional facial expression it may be interpreted as a threat and opinion, and on a written paper/written text it may be interpreted as an advice.

1.2 Objectives of the Research.

The change in meaning, function, and intention due to influence of facial expressions and prosodic emotions to an utterance linguistic content is of high concern to both semiotics and pragmatics.

In phonetics studies, there are evidence on acoustic detectability of prosodic physiological features such as excitation, energy, duration, and loudness manifesting when the same utterance is spoken to indicate different attitude and intentions such as question and statement intonation. (Ladd, 1996; Vaissière, 2004; Fonagy, 1981; Hirschberg & Ward, 1992; Ward & Hirschberg, 1988; Bolinger, 1964; House, 2003). However, there are still inadequate approaches to how emotional facial expressions, prosodic emotions, and linguistic content of an utterance interact to create different meanings, functions, and intentions.

Thus, the motivating reason for setting objectives of this research is the complexity and absence of one to one relationship between emotion categories and intonation categories, and inability of intonation analysis tools to detect multi-modal utterance intention (an intentional matched and mismatched emotional utterance) rather than intonational utterance intentions, since emotions are not sounds and sounds are not emotions even though they can both be used to conditions different utterance meanings and intentions, and can both still be detected differently in acoustic analysis tools.

For this reason, this thesis covers two objectives, which are,

- A. First, laying down foundations to studying pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and an utterance.
- B. Second, finding evidence supporting presence of pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of a face, voice, and an utterance in interlocution.

To enquire the essence of changes in meanings, functions, and intentions due to emotional signification, two phonetics experiments have been applied.

The first experiment was designed to find out acoustic differences in an English utterance when spoken in eight different emotional expressions and found mean amplitudes differences. With the aid of Praat speech analysis software, the ready constructed ten English utterances which were spoken by ten different speakers each in eight different emotional expressions were recorded for experiment analysis.

It was then hypothesized that, since emotions as carriers of utterance meanings may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intention of an utterance unless there are theoretical explanations of how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions, there was therefore an additional utterance intention listener judgement experiment which used matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses to dialogues formulated by consulting explanations laid in the theoretical foundation part that not all types of sentence and or classes of Searle speech acts react similarly in terms of utterance function and intention when affected by emotional signification.

The second phonetic experiment was designed to determine whether different emotional categories of one speech/utterance presupposed to have specific functions and intentions could be physically comprehended by English listeners. In this experiment English listeners responded to multiple choice survey questions attached with English dialogues by selecting the speaker's intention from four options from each dialogue.

Therefore, this research describes an approach to understanding utterance meanings, functions, and intentions which are present in matches and mismatches of emotional facial expressions, voice emotions and utterance linguistic content during interlocution by focusing on the concept 'emotional signification' using two theoretical foundations which are, Emotional signification as a semiotic process, and emotional signification as a pragmatic act, and two research methods which are two phonetics experiments which are; Utterance emotion categories distinction experiment and speech acts emotional signification phonetic experiment, and one linguistic survey about Utterance intention listener judgement.

1.3 Significance of the Research.

This research explains an approach to understanding interrelationship between the face, voice, and an utterance in interlocution. It lays down foundations to studying meanings, functions, and intentions through an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and an utterance in two theoretical foundations, which are, Emotional signification as a semiotic process and Emotional signification as a pragmatic act.

1.4 Thesis Structure.

This thesis is organized into six chapters. Chapter 1, introduces statements, research objectives, research significance and thesis structure. Chapter 2 provides a literature review. Chapter 3 lays down a theoretical foundation of the research. Chapter 4 presents a research methodology. Chapter 5 presents research analysis and results. Chapter 6 presents research discussion and conclusion.

CHAPTER TWO LITERATURE REVIEW

Communication acts are complex human interaction behaviors. The choice of meanings to attach to communication acts can be semantic, pragmatic, or semiotic based on factors which are accountable for change in meanings of a communication act or an utterance. Such factors may be due to speech community social linguistic conventions, social motivation, or independent general intelligence.

Defining the property of language where a language user conditions and recognize conditioned pragmatic emotional meanings, functions and intentions through an interplay and mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and an utterance as '*Emotional signification*' is, primarily, regarding an utterance/sentence as a semiotic sign. This is because the influences to references of an utterance/sentence are caused by emotions which are presented in facial expressions of both felt emotions and unfelt emotions (false mental states) operating as semiotic indexes of emotion along with other factors such as reference 'of facial expression' as a component of meaning of an utterance, and truth conditions of an act of speech.

Linguists study the change in meaning of an utterance through three different fields which are semiotics, pragmatics, and semantics. The change in meaning studied in each of the three fields is based on different contributing factors in each field.

Semantics deals with utterance meanings as formulated in the sentence surface structure. The change in meaning, function, and intention due to influence of facial expressions and prosodic emotions to an utterance linguistic content which has been referred to as '*Emotional signification*' is of high concern to semiotics and pragmatics.

Pragmatics is the field in linguistics that deals with indirect meanings of an utterance based on contributing factors such as context, mental states, and neighboring speech or text forms. A pragmatic meaning is an indirect meaning of an utterance which comes from factors other than the surface structure of an utterance such as context, mental states, and neighboring speech/text. Reference is defined in pragmatics as a thing that the speaker says or writes that mentions something or somebody else, and as the act of mentioning somebody or something (Oxford Advanced Learner Dictionary, 10th Edition). According to Mey (2010), reference making is "a situated process (as is speech acting itself);", and "what the speaker have in mind

as the reference for an utterance, depends on what the responding interlocutors can have in mind as the possible referents for that utterance—and in fact on what the entire societal situation ‘represents’ for the speaker and his/her interlocutors., even non-linguistic behavior can be referential (a smile, a nod, a shrug, etc.). But all reference must refer to the situation in which reference takes place; the single person making a reference establishes it only in connection with the other participants in the situation”.

A communication act leading to a pragmatic meaning is a pragmatic act. Kecskes (2010) defined a pragmatic act as ‘an act of adapting oneself to a context, as well as adapting the context to oneself.’. It is any intentional use of mental states, context, or neighboring speech or texts in an utterance to present an indirect meaning of an utterance which is different from the surface structure semantic meaning. Pragmatic acts include speech acts, conversation implicatures, and other indirect meanings such as insincerity, politeness, and humor. Conditioning utterances meanings using emotion categories for different functions and intentions serves as a speech act. The concept ‘Speech act’ was introduced by Oxford philosopher J.L. Austin in the book *‘How to Do Things with Words’* and further developed by American philosopher J.R. Searle. Speech act theory explains how utterances are said to perform locutionary acts, illocutionary acts, and perlocutionary acts. A speech act is an utterance capable of performing an action based on the speaker’s intention or effect of an utterance. (Austin, 1962a; Searle, 1979).

The influences to references of an utterance/sentence caused by emotions displayed via facial expressions of unfeared emotions (false mental states) can be described as the function of emotion indexes operating in a semiotic process. Semiotics is the study of signs and their meanings. A sign is anything that has meaning, A sign may be in concrete form, gesture form, written form or spoken form. Semioticians categorize signs into three categories, which are symbols, icons, and indexes. A symbol has a conventional reference to its vehicle, E.g., a question mark. An icon has an identical reference with its vehicle, E.g., a toilet door’s icon. And an index has a causative reference with its vehicle E.g., an emotion emoji. (Atkin, 2010; Liszka, 1996). A semiotic process is therefore a process of making meaning of a sign based on different forms of a sign. In emotional conversation, the meanings conditioned by the choice of form of an emotion index or change of reference of an emotion index as a component of a semiotic sign such as facial expressions accompanying an utterance, or an emoji attached in front of a sentence in online chatting platforms such as WeChat, WhatsApp, or Facebook, is what accounts for conditioning and recognition of conditioned

semiotic references of an utterance. A semiotic process creates reference of a sign based on different forms of a sign. It may also mean the change from one direct meaning (reference of a sign) to another direct meaning (another reference of a sign). Unlike pragmatic meanings, which Mey (2010) puts as ‘what the speaker have in mind as the reference for an utterance, depends on what the responding interlocutors can have in mind as the possible referents for that utterance’, A semiotic meaning, on the other hand, relies on the surface structure of an utterance and its possible references due to the form that a sign has. The question on a precise definition of a semiotic process/meaning making process, should go back to ‘who creates signs (symbols, icons, and indexes) such as road traffic signs, toilet icons, or emotion indexes and emojis’ and ‘why creators of signs create signs in the form that they have then attempt to make modifications to the forms of such signs for different intentions and functions?’. The process of choosing or modifying a form of a sign to carry a particular reference/meaning, is what is the semiotic process/meaning making process. This is because the choice or modification of different forms of the same sign for different functions and intentions may derive a different reference that is not intended. E.g., the difference between men’s toilet icon, women toilet icons, and gays’ toilet icons, is on their difference as forms of a sign of a person. They are closely related to the form of an icon of a person standing still drawn at the door, but with slight difference in forms of their icons. Changing the form of men’s toilet icon and women’s toilet icon to that of gays’ toilet icon to meet specific intentions and functions is what counts as a semiotic process. It is the same as making slight modifications to the form of ‘an utterance as linguistic sign’, for different intentions and functions when doing communication such as when speaking. Speaking is the presentation of reference of a linguistic expression with a particular emotion form in three modalities i.e., voice, facial expression, and utterance. The intentional changing of a form of emotion index/expression accompanying an utterance from an assumed ‘basic semantic emotion form’ to another emotion category by means of modifications of speech modality to serve different function and intention is also a semiotic process/a meaning making process, as it renders newer reference to an utterance.

Conditioning and recognizing conditioned pragmatic emotional meanings, functions and intentions through an interplay and mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and an utterance involves different factors accountable for change in meanings of an utterance, which are, mental states, reference ‘of facial expression’ as a component of meaning, signs (facial expressions as emotional indexes), and truth

conditions (The truth of an utterance proposition in a matched emotional utterance or mismatched emotional utterance).

In emotional signification, mental states, and truth conditions as contributing factors to change in utterance meaning are studied in pragmatics, reference is studied in both pragmatics and semiotics, and signs and signification are studied in semiotics. Mental states are conscious and unconscious feelings indicating a person's state of mind. They may be indicated by true or false facial expressions of emotions. (Bucciarelli et al., 2003; Bosco, 2006). A sentence in semiotics is regarded as a verbal sign with its reference/meaning. According to Yakin & Totu (2014), A sign is resulted from an imagination or an activity of human minds that is expressed through language codes and understood by the individuals who are involved in the communication process. A sign, according to Saussure, is something delivered by someone with a purpose and specific meaning intentionally, i.e., a process or a phenomenon that does not occur coincidentally or by chance. This means that according to Saussure, nothing is a sign unless it is interpreted as a sign.

Also, Facial emotion indexes which forms another modality of speech apart from an utterance as a sign, are not necessarily semiotic references of mental states, they may be intentionally displayed independent of mental states/state of mind, as signs with other truth conditions other than reference/denotation of the state of mind. On the other hand, A truth condition, in pragmatics, is a condition under which a sentence proposition is true. A sentence/utterance proposition is true if the verbal action or state of reference exists at the point of reference. For instance, if a person says, 'I am happy' while showing sadness and crying, the psychological state 'happiness', introduced by the verb to be: 'am', shows an utterance is lacking a truth condition. i.e., happiness does not exist in the speaker's mental state/state of mind at that time denoted by the present tense 'am'. Based on Birner (2012) and Papafragou (2006).

Comprehending utterance's differences in meanings when spoken and accompanied with facial expressions of different types require interlocutors to have specific knowledge competence in the use of language. The following review explains a course of overviews regarding such usage.

2.1 Previous Studies on Emotional Signification for Language Competence.

Developing foreign language competence takes a variety of aspects which cannot be mastered all at once. Foreign language competence includes linguistic competence, discourse competence, sociolinguistic competence, and strategic competence. (Chomsky, 1965; Hymes, 1966). Most academicians emphasize linguistic competence, which starts with vocabulary proficiency and goes on with grammar drawing on four language skills, namely, listening, speaking, reading, and writing.

However, for the language user to interact effectively, as required and as expected by other users of the same or different sociolinguistic groups, he/she needs to have mental abilities in producing language forms understood by the counterparts, comprehending language forms from counterparts and the will to perform as expected by the counterparts without breaking communication needs of both parts. Such knowledge is referred by linguists as social linguistic competence. Its cognition is revealed by speaker's world view as they communicate which encompasses the language system as it is related to worldly concepts, worldly facts, and events happening in the surrounding language community.

Vocabulary proficiency as part of linguistic competence, which is mostly emphasized by academicians, is an ability to apply acquired word knowledge in language related contexts. Linguists have tried defining aspects with which learning a vocabulary revolves. Cronbach (1942, pp. 206-217) suggests five aspects involved in knowing a word, which are: Generalization, Application, Breadth of word's meaning, Exactness and Flexibility. Scholars such as Qian (2002, pp. 513-536) and Nayan (2018) insist on Depth and Breadth (vocabulary size). Qian (2002, pp. 513-536) focuses on three elements of the depth meaning of vocabulary knowledge, namely, synonymy, polysemy, and collocations, in reading comprehension. Qian (2002, p. 515) defines 'Breadth of vocabulary knowledge' as "the size of vocabulary or the number of words which one has at least some superficial knowledge of", and 'Depth of vocabulary knowledge' as "how well one knows a word.". Qian (2002) note out 'the obvious weakness' in Cronbach (1942) early definition of vocabulary knowledge which divides vocabulary knowledge into knowledge of word meaning (generalization, breadth of meaning, and precision of meaning) and levels of accessibility to this knowledge (availability and application), that, the definition lack a place for other aspects of lexical knowledge, such as spelling, pronunciation, morpho-syntactic properties, and collocation. Thus, Qian

(2002) redefines Vocabulary knowledge using a conceptual framework of vocabulary knowledge comprising the four dimensions, namely: (a) vocabulary size; (b) depth of vocabulary knowledge, which includes all word characteristics such as phonemic, graphemic, morphemic, syntactic, semantic, collocational and phraseological properties; (c) lexical organization, which refers to the storage, connection, and representation of words in the mental lexicon; and (d) automaticity of receptive productive knowledge, which refers to all fundamental processes through which access to word knowledge is achieved for both receptive and productive purposes. He builds the argument on reformulation of the framework of vocabulary knowledge based on Mezynski (1983, p. 265), who noted that “word meanings can be ‘known’ to varying degrees. Depending on the task, a person could perform adequately with relatively imprecise knowledge. In other situations, a much finer notion of the word’s meaning might be required”, where Qian (2002) emphasizes that “although sometimes L2 learners need only partial knowledge of a word in comprehension, more lexical knowledge is obviously desirable in many situations”. Richards (1976) proposes seven aspects of vocabulary knowledge which are: frequency, register, syntax, derivation, association, semantic features, and polysemy. Nation (2001) extends Richards (1976) aspects of vocabulary knowledge into form (written and spoken), Position (Grammar and Collocation), Function (Frequency and Appropriateness), and Meaning (Concept and Collocation). This follows his analysis of a series of questions about ‘Learning Vocabulary in Another Language’ where he applies a corpus study of texts from different fields where he distinguishes four kinds of vocabulary in texts: namely, high-frequency words, academic words, technical words, and low-frequency words. He also suggests ways of learning and teaching words and strategies for testing vocabulary knowledge by identifying imbalances in learning workloads between learners high-frequency words and low-frequency words.

In this research, to solve sociolinguistic problems of English language which results into emotional utterances pragmatic communication errors, there is a need to observe English language as a tool of communication where a proficient English speaker should know ‘meanings’, ‘functions’, and ‘intentions’ of words and utterances in different usage, including matching and mismatching of linguistic contents, facial expressions, and voice emotions. In real life communication one of the problems facing communication using English as a foreign language is English emotional language incompetence i.e., misrepresentation, and misinterpretation of emotional utterances and emotional facial expressions

accompanying emotional utterances. Therefore, to produce competent sociolinguistic users of English language as a foreign language such as good debaters, good negotiators, good film actors/actresses, and good public speakers, the focus needs to be on attaining EFL sociolinguistic competence in both formal and informal learning contexts.

Based on the precluded source of the problem that may be multi-diversity of semiotics and culture, Ekman et al. (1987), conducted research about universals and cultural differences in the judgements of facial expressions of emotion by speculating cross-cultural agreement in judgement of facial expressions and found cultural evidence in judgements of absolute levels of emotional intensity. Subsequent studies on cultural foundations for facial expressions accompanying non-verbal linguistic emotional signification lay basic cultural and semiotic approaches to this research which includes, how culture differ in degree to which language users accurately perceive universal emotions in Matsumoto (1992), How emotions are viewed as having evolved through their adaptive value in dealing with fundamental life-tasks in Ekman (1992), and How Asians express specific emotions contrary to Westerners, such as what Jack et al. (2009) figure out to be the use of culture-specific decoding strategy by Asians that is considered inadequate to reliably distinguish universal facial expressions of 'fear' and 'disgust'. In western cultures, for instance, they note Asians to be persistently fixating the eye region when expressing fear and disgust which confuse westerners. Later, Jack et al. (2012) gave what may be a conclusive remark that "facial expressions of emotion are not culturally universal". On the other hand, Liu (2014), agree on the same claims about culture based emotional signification but with different approaches which pose challenges on the adequate intensity of emotion signification, as he poses his findings on Chinese people to have low anger expression intensity compared to Americans. Another research on culture and semiotics as the source of this research problem is that of Benitez-Garcia et al. (2017) which speculates facial muscles and organs movements, appearance, intensity, and geometry to propose the differences in cultural emotional signification between East-Asians and Westerners.

Therefore, emotional signification as a form of language competence may be semiotic and cultural and may vary based on different cultural or personal motivations.

2.2 Previous Studies on Emotional Signification Through Words and Utterances in China.

Linguistic representations of Chinese facial expressions, which according to Ye (2004) represent a local facial encoding system, provide valuable resources with which researchers can obtain a culture-internal view of the perceptions and conceptions of the face. Ye (2004) speculates the Chinese Folk model of facial expressions in a linguistic perspective, taking the notion of ‘folk’ as opposed to scientific Facial Action Coding system (FACS) developed by Ekman and Friesen (1978) to provide raw psychological conceptual evidence linking emotions and facial expressions.

The explicit and implicit view of emotional signs and meanings by Chinese people is expressed linguistically through Chinese idioms (Chengyu) related to body language, culture specific words, and cultural expression of politeness. The set phrase and idioms (four characters long), constitute psycholinguistic revelation of Chinese perception of emotions and their meanings. It is approximated that 48.8 percent of Chengyu refer to facial expressions (including references to the face and the components of the face). (Yang, 1998, as cited from Ye, 2004). Ye (2004) suggests on Chengyu as the most reliable linguistic evidence for Chinese basis of perception and expression of emotional vocabulary. On the other hand, facial emotional expressions have been investigated and found to be essential in expressions of Politeness. For instance, Zhu and Bao (2010) research on “The Pragmatic Comparison of Chinese and Western “Politeness” in Cross-cultural Communication” express the concepts of politeness in Chinese culture noting Professor Gu Yueguo’s book on Pragmatic Politeness and Culture, that, there are four basic concepts in traditional Chinese politeness which are, respectfulness, modesty, attitudinal warmth, and refinement (which he describes as choosing elegant expression and forbidding bawdry). Zhu and Bao (2010) conclude that, in cross-cultural communication, people should do their best to use the correct politeness principle, avoid cultural conflict and get the best effect of communication.

2.3 Previous Studies on Emotional Signification Through Words and Utterances Outside China.

Linguistic philosophers have long acknowledged the meaning of ‘meaning’ in their explanations of functions and intentions of speech forms. Wittgenstein (1953, p. 43) found Meaning and Use to be systematically related, and that, meaning of a word is its use. Frege (1977) divides meaning into three components; Force, Sense, and Denotation. According to Frege, Force is determined by expression’s meaning. Vanderveken and Kubo (2001, p. 2) explain a propositional force ‘of assertion’ - to be acknowledging the truths of expressed propositions in a literal utterance of a declarative sentence, and a propositional force ‘of question’ – to be serving the questioning for a response in a literal utterance of an interrogative sentence.

The truth which is being acknowledged i.e., how are things supposed to be, and not supposed to be, when indirectly stated through the speaker emotional state accompanying an utterance and fail to be acknowledged by the hearer as firstly acknowledged by the speaker, it affects the hearer’s semiotic process (process of making meaning) based on underlying assumptions presented by emotional facial expressions, and thus, affecting an assertion to have contents related to an emotive force denoting the speaker’s state of mind.

For instance, suppose an utterance ‘Sir, you are standing on my foot’ given in (Searle 1979, p. viii) is spoken by accompanying it with sadness facial expressions, the hearer (Sir) is likely convinced to acknowledge a verbal action of standing on the speaker’s foot to be ‘measured as sad’, ‘causing sadness’, and or ‘deserving sadness’ and if spoken in a happiness emotional facial expression, the hearer assumes the verbal action ‘as measured as happy’, ‘causing happiness’, and or ‘deserving happiness’. Now the problem comes, when the hearer schema perceives such a verbal action of standing on the speaker’s foot as ‘not measured as happy’, ‘not causing happiness’, and ‘not deserving happiness’, when this happens the hearer is emotively forced, with another emotive force, to create a reference in mind regarding an intention and function of using a happiness facial expression to accompany an utterance ‘Sir, you are standing on my foot’.

Of course, an assumption might come to mind, of an interplay or mismatches of an utterance and facial expression, as being polite, and whether that's how saying such an utterance in a polite way is supposed to be, or whether there are different categories or degrees of happiness suitable for accompanying politeness and those not suitable for accompanying politeness. Presumably, other speakers may present similar interplay or mismatches of speech forms using different figures of emotive forces such as politeness, silence, or even verbosity. Those choosing to present the same assertion with politeness might as well choose to use different figures of politeness as explained in Section 2.2 above the way Chinese Chengyu has politeness emotive force divided into four, namely, Respectfulness, Modesty, Attitudinal warmth, and Refinement in Zhu and Bao (2010). Now, when an assertion is presented through an interplay of an utterance and facial expression and fails to be acknowledged as intended by the speaker, its function gets risked by its emotive force leading to non-verbal pragmatic failure. Du (2014) gives an account of non-verbal pragmatic failure in intercultural communication where he includes facial expressions consciousness as the key towards the strategy to avoid or reduce pragmatic failures to provide some useful reference for people engaging in intercultural communication. To compare emotional signification through facial expressions inside and outside China, he cites from the major Chinese tribe, The Han nationality who greet their honored guests with a smile when guests arrive; while American Indian tribes greet their guests with a cry, to show that only understanding the different meanings of facial expressions in different cultures can avoid pragmatic failure of non-verbal behavior. Matthews (2012) adds that, culture can affect how a person perceives the actions of others which means the Han nationality and American Indian tribes welcome greetings may easily get misunderstood by other non-Chinese societies who have the smile and crying facial expressions reserved for other 'first encounter-related functions and intentions' apart from accompanying greetings.

When observing the relationship between three components of meaning i.e., Force, Sense and Denotation, Sense, of a sentence, according to Vanderveken and Kubo (2001, p. 19), may be regarded as a proposition with truth conditions, and content of a sentence is a proposition with success and satisfaction conditions. Sense is simply a literal meaning stated in terms of truth conditions of a verbal action or state in a sentence. Sense may be changed by facial expressions because facial expressions contain an emotive force that is indirectly affecting a propositional force of a sentence. In other words, facial expressions can change truth

conditions by totally creating a new reference(denotation) of a sentence, deviate a reference(denotation), or affect the degree of a reference (an expression of a literal meaning of a sentence) so as to serve different functions and intentions including politeness. Politeness means presenting the sense (a proposition with truth conditions) in different degree of reference/denotation. Applying a facial expression emotive force may mask a direct expression of an utterance surface structure such as a harsh meaning to be perceived as less harsh, not harsh, or different. Thus, an emotive force of a facial expression may change an utterance truth conditions and lead to 'change in content' and 'change in sense'. 'Content' varies from 'proposition content' in a sense that, a propositional content is a verbal action or state which is implicitly or explicitly stated in the sentence, and which contains sincerity conditions such as attitude, state, regret, intention, pleasure etc., Propositional content of the same utterance such as 'Congratulations!' can be used in different settings to state different sincerity conditions both implicitly and explicitly. Searle (1979, pp.12-19) proposes an alternative taxonomy to Austin (1962a) speech acts, stating that, speech acts have propositional contents expressed as states, intentions, attitude, etc., In this alternative taxonomy of speech acts, Propositional contents may indirectly be used to perform an illocutionary act of a goal such as belief, wish or desire, intention, psychological state, or declaration by means of what in this research is found and described as 'a transfiguration through an emotive force of a facial expression'. This may happen by changing the propositional force of an illocutionary act across sincerity conditions (both sincerity and insincerity) such as 'from belief to intention', 'from state to wish', 'from intention to state', or 'from state to intention'. For instance, in an utterance 'He is coming' spoken in an angry emotive force, the change in an emotive force from neutral to angry affects a propositional force that is in the semantic structure of a sentence by 'shifting focus' of an utterance from the speaker's mere propositional assertion of 'a verbal action supplying information to the object about the topic him coming' to 'an intentional angry emotive function attached to an utterance' which measures a verbal action as forced by an emotive force to be 'measured as angry', 'causing anger', or 'deserving anger'. This 'shift in focus' from 'belief to intention' is an indirect change in propositional force of an utterance.

2.4 EFL Emotional Vocabulary acquisition.

When told to prepare for speeches, presentations, debates, and meetings, English as a foreign language (EFL) learners tend to dive deep down the language norms and speaking styles, coping, and trying to assimilate, contemplating comprehensively and incomprehensively, what they perceive to be likeable and funny styles, as it is done by the native English speakers. However, the same EFL learners, when in an immediate unprepared totally new face to face encounters, they may be faced with difficulties with ‘instant in-brain interpretation’ during the same act of speaking and thus giving out reflecting raw psycholinguistic cues such as excessive energy and interlanguage errors containing emotive forces, senses, and references as applied in their mother tongues.

Pamugkas and Wulandari (2020) propose teaching English Pragmatics and Culture as a strategy to enable EFL students’ mastery of EFL intercultural pragmatic competence noting that, “It is considered to be a demanding task to properly act and behave in another culture”. According to Jie (2010), when a teacher goes to train culture in a language class, he/she should prepare at least three objectives: “(1) To get the students familiar with cultural differences; (2) To help the students transcend their own cultures and see things as the members of the target culture; and (3) To emphasize the inseparability of understanding language and understanding culture through various classroom practices”. Thus, the mastery of knowledge of English pragmatic facial expressions can be effectively done by considering facial expressions accompanying utterances as expressed in the language’s mother culture.

Other methods which have been suggested to fit Chinese EFL vocabulary acquisition contexts include “rote learning” (Ballard & Clanchy, 1984; Bradley & Bradley, 1984; Samuelowicz, 1987; Yongqi 2003), and “repetitive learning” as opposed to rote learning in Watkins and Biggs (1996). Outside China, given the abstract nature of emotions in facial expressions, as part of EFL abstract nouns mastery, research works on emotional signification have been conducted to propose whether the mastery of abstract vocabulary can be achieved using images in English classes to improve motivation and learner’s activeness in classroom acquisition process which proves that “The students who are taught using pictures have better vocabulary mastery than those who are taught using a conventional method”. (Astuti, 2008; Jatmiko & Jauhari, 2018). English emotional vocabulary images may assist learners’ development of ideas and

imagination if the EFL teacher allows learner's active participation, learners centered pedagogy and homework. Based on Elsy (2013).

2.5 Detection of matched and mismatched emotional speech signal.

Attempts to identify and detect acoustic manifestation of physiological features of emotion in matched and mismatched emotional speeches have been done in a variety of ways and fields. They all regard a speech signal as composite of emotion information at different parts of an utterance and in the entire sentence (in an utterance as a whole). The features most investigated in matched and mismatched emotional speech signal identification and detection include, Excitation source features, emotion category of a speech, and speaker's attitude.

Excitation contains emotion specific information which can be detected by higher order relations in linear prediction (LP) residual samples. In Koolagudi et al. (2012) the variations in excitation characteristics are distinguished by the glottal wave and its derivative whereby the amplitude of excitation pulses (often termed as strength of excitation), and their periodicity (pitch contour) are also affected by the emotions. In Prasanna and Govind (2010) glottal waveforms and their derivative indicate that boredom and neutral emotions have relatively higher excitation strength and fear emotion has the least strength of excitation compared to four different emotions, namely, neutral, angry, happy, and boredom. Also, glottal wave derivative shows that anger and fear have the highest pitch and boredom and neutral emotion have lowest pitch. In Kadiri et al. (2015) excitation source features are extracted from Subsegmental features related to excitation source information. The subsegmental features detected include instantaneous fundamental frequency (F0), strength of excitation (SoE) and energy of excitation (EoE). These features are extracted using zero frequency filtering (ZFF) method used in Yegnanarayana and Murty (2009) and linear prediction (LP) analysis used in Makhoul (1975) for developing a system for automatic recognition of emotions based on emotional deviations of speeches. The results indicate that the features corresponding to vocal effort at subsegmental level seem to carry emotion-specific information.

On the other hand, Phrasing, which is one way utterance meaning may be conditioned differently in the same spoken utterance, is defined by Ahn et al. (2021, p. 18) as how words are grouped, so that some are

perceived with no disjuncture between them (i.e., they are perceived as sounding closely grouped together), and some words are perceived as having (various levels of) disjuncture between them. Phrasing can be done at a syntactical level, with intonation, or with emotions. For example, the sentence; ‘-Steve or Sam and Bob will come’ can be rephrased into ‘-Steve, or Sam and Bob, will come’, and ‘-Steve or Sam, and Bob, will come’ to mark different prominence, meanings, and utterance intentions. (Ahn et al., 2021; Lehiste 1973; Price et al., 1991; Veilleux et al., 2006.)

Identification and detectability of Speech emotion categories uses different approaches. There are research works detecting speech emotion category at an utterance level, in a corpus, dialogue, and in continuous speech. Koolagudi et al. (2012) uses corpus-based research to detect sad, angry, happy, and neutral emotions from speech using Linear Prediction (LP) residual of speech signal where inverse filtering is applied to a speech signal and Gaussian mixture models (GMM) are used to capture emotion specific information from the higher order relations present in Linear Prediction residual samples with 50% to 60% emotion recognition accuracy. The results do not show utterance specific differences between emotion categories nor does the research indicate differences used as a criterion in Gaussian mixture models used in recognizing and distinguishing sad, angry, happy, and neutral speeches, instead, they train emotion specific models to detect one emotion category after another from the corpus using an algorithm that is special for finding maximum likelihood estimates of parameters in probabilistic models. Prasanna and Govind (2010) analyze the effect of emotions on the excitation source of speech production. The neutral, angry, happy, boredom and fear emotions are considered for the study. Initially the electro glotto gram (EGG) and its derivative signals are compared across different emotions. The mean, standard deviation and contour of instantaneous pitch, and strength of excitation parameters are derived by processing the derivative of the EGG and also speech using zero-frequency filtering (ZFF) approach. The comparative study of these features across different emotions reveals that the effect of emotions on the excitation source is distinct and significant. Prasanna and Govind (2010) distinguish speech emotions by studying and analyzing the Electro Glotto Gram (EGG) signals of various emotions. EGG represents the actual glottal waveform that is produced by closing and opening of vocal folds during speech production where the difference in five different emotions, namely, neutral, angry, happy, boredom and fear of the same speaker and sounds, manifests in terms of speech waveform, LP spectrum, glottal waveform, and glottal wave

derivative. The accuracy of the difference in speech emotion categories is based on speaker's individuality since the speaker and sounds are the same and the variations across different plots are primarily due to emotions.

Other research works identifying speech emotions using both one and a mixture of emotion physiological features conduct acoustic identification of speech emotions based on manifestation of their differences in such acoustic features. For instance, Disgust is identified with glottalization and pharyngealization in Vaissière (2004, p. 15). Anger is identified with F_0 irregularities, forceful innervation of the glottal muscles, narrow constriction of the glottal space as well as retracted lips and tongue retraction in Fonagy (2000) who investigates tomographic and cineradiographic studies. Anger is also identified with the highest pitch in glottal wave derivative, as compared to four other emotions namely neutral, angry, happy, boredom, whereby pitch increases and hence pitch periodicity decreases. To cater the smaller values to periodicity, the vocal folds may not be closing with high suction and hence low strength for impulse like excitation. (Prasanna & Govind, 2010). Surprise is identified with Raised eyebrows and often go hand in hand with an F_0 rise in the expression of surprise in Fonagy (2000). Fear is identified with the highest pitch in glottal wave derivative as compared to four other emotions namely neutral, angry, happy, boredom. Boredom is identified with lowest pitch in glottal wave derivative as compared to four other emotions namely neutral, angry, happy, boredom and Neutral emotion is identified with lowest pitch in glottal wave derivative as compared to four other emotions namely neutral, angry, happy, boredom. (Prasanna & Govind, 2010).

There are other research works focusing on identification and detection of speech and speaker's attitude which resembles what may be the result of the conditioning of matched and mismatched emotional speech signal detection. For instance, speeches of different emotional attitudes have been found to be identifiable with different acoustic and physiological features. For example, Identification of Agreeable emotions with Melodicity (Vaissière, 2004; Fonagy, 1981). Identification of Disagreeable emotions with Lack of melodicity (Vaissière, 2004; Fonagy, 1981). Identification of Excitement with Higher pitch, where the degree of general excitement and tension (arousal) is reflected in the degree of tension of the vocal folds in Vaissière (2004, p. 15). Identification of Detachment with Low F_0 (and a slower speaking rate) in Vaissière (2004, p. 15). Identification of Activeness with Rapid speech in Vaissière (2004, p. 16), Identification of Subordinate, submissive, non-threatening, desirous of the receiver's goodwill, polite, lack

of threat by the subject, more femininity, hesitation, uncertainty, or surprise with High Fo and breathiness. (Vaissière, 2004; Hirschberg & Ward, 1992; Ward & Hirschberg, 1988). Identification of Incredulity with Greater pitch range. (Vaissière, 2004; Hirschberg & Ward, 1992; Ward & Hirschberg, 1988). Identification of Uncertainty with smaller pitch range. (Vaissière, 2004; Hirschberg & Ward, 1992; Ward & Hirschberg, 1988). Identification of aggressive, threatening, definitive, more authority with Lower formants, lower Fo and the creaky quality of the voice. (Vaissière, 2004; Bolinger, 1964).

However, difficulties with identification of utterance intention using specific acoustic or physiological features tend to appear due to difference between Nativism and second language due to mother tongue influence. For instance, House (2003, p. 755) cited Ladd (1996) who indicated that; “not only does question intonation vary in different languages but also different types of questions (e.g., wh, yes/no or echo questions) result in different kinds of question intonation”.

Therefore, identification and detection of acoustic manifestation of physiological features of emotion in matched and mismatched emotional speeches are possible in linguistics and speech acoustics and have been done in a variety of ways and fields and are all regarding a speech signal as composite of emotion information at different parts of an utterance and in the entire sentence (in an utterance as a whole). However, Emotions as carriers of utterance meanings may not when detected in acoustic analysis tools may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intention of an utterance. Therefore, there has to be a theoretical explanation on how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions such as matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses in English dialogues.

The above literature review has enquired research works on comprehension of utterance's differences in meaning when spoken and accompanied with facial expressions of different types, as a specific form of language competence (emotional signification competence). The chapter has highlighted such competence from other language related competence as required in solving socio-linguistic problems of English language. Semiotic and culture have been investigated as precluded sources of interplay and or mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and utterance which contributes to meanings, functions, and intentions. One noted function of emotional signification has been found to be 'showing politeness'. Other meaning

making processes through emotional signification have been shown to be resulting from introduction of an emotive force which competes with utterance's surface structure propositional force. Unawareness of EFL learners learning language specific cultural values has also been related to the precluded source of emotional signification challenge. The chapter is also showing the review of research works attempting to identify and detect acoustic manifestation of physiological features of emotion in speech whereby the reviewed research works regard a speech signal as composite of emotion information at different parts of an utterance and in the entire sentence (as a whole) and are mostly investigating matched and mismatched emotional speech signal identification and detection including, Excitation source features, emotion category of a speech, and speaker's attitude. Finally, the literature review indicates that identification and detection of acoustic manifestation of physiological features of emotion in matched and mismatched emotional utterances are possible in linguistics and speech acoustics and have been done in a variety of ways and fields and are all regarding a speech signal as composite of emotion information at different parts of an utterance and in the entire sentence (in an utterance as a whole).

What is yet to be researched which the following chapters will cover is empirical enquiries on the scope of emotional significations on how speakers express and interpret emotionally signified utterances, and what pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions are presented when an utterance is spoken in different emotion categories. And, since emotions as carriers of utterance meanings despite being identifiable and detectable in speech acoustics may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intentions of a matched and mismatched emotional utterance, the next chapter is thus laying down the theoretical foundation on how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions such as matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses in English dialogues as an empirical investigation of the first objective of this thesis whose confirmation empirical data will be investigated in the methodology chapter.

CHAPTER THREE THEORETICAL FOUNDATION

In this Chapter I'm presenting and discussing the concept 'Emotional signification' as an approach to understanding a pragmatic emotional utterance involving interrelationship and mismatches between facial expressions, voice, and utterance words in interlocution.

An English emotional utterance 'I'm so happy to meet you' when accompanied with different emotional facial expressions at different contexts appears to be conditioned, or rather signified, in a way that it changes meanings, functions, and intentions due to such emotional facial expressions.

Well, before getting further, it's obvious that it would bring interests to a discourse analyst to observe 'an interplayed and mismatched emotional utterance'- 'I'm so happy to meet you', since -it may contain meanings beyond the sentence surface structure, -it sounds functional specific, and -it may be applied in different settings to imply different meanings including settings where people are not supposed to express happiness expressions when they first meet, as it is the case for a nurse meeting a very ill patient in a hospital, which turns the discourse analyst focus onto 'oddness of an utterance' rather than a mismatched facial expression or prosody accompanying an utterance. However, for the sake of empirical inquiries on possible 'meanings', 'functions', and 'intentions', this research is otherwise investigating a semiotic foundation (meaning making processes) and speculating pragmatic foundations for 'meanings, functions, and intentions' as a pragmatic act.

Thus, the property of linguistics where a language user conditions and recognize conditioned pragmatic emotional meanings, functions, and intentions through an interplay and mismatching of a facial expression, voice, and an utterance has been regarded as 'Emotional signification'.

3.1 Emotional Signification as a Semiotic Process.

A semiotic process is a process of making meaning of a sign. A sign is anything which has meaning. E.g., a word, an utterance, a painting etc., Meaning is the relationship between a sign and its reference. The meaning of a word/utterance is made up of sense, force, and reference. Sense is a mode of presentation (structure of presentation). Force is an intended state of reference. Reference is the truth value of a sign/sentence/utterance.

Due to change in sense, force, and reference, the meaning of a sign/sentence may be changed from directness to indirectness. When this happens, the function and intention of an utterance may be affected as well. Function is an activity that may happen to a person, thing, or world due to verbal action(s) or state(s) expressed in the sentence with or without the speaker being aware e.g., warning, requesting, promising, amusing, ridiculing, accepting, convincing, pleasing, embarrassing, influencing, or Schadenfreude which means a pleasure gained by laughing at other's misfortunes. Intention is an activity a speaker wants to happen by means of a verbal action or state expressed directly or indirectly in a sentence. E.g., to warn, to request, to promise, to amuse, to ridicule, to accept, to convince, to please, to embarrass, to influence, or to laugh at others' misfortunes. There are four factors accountable for change in meaning of a sign/sentence/utterance which may lead to change in functions and intentions in both direct and indirect ways. The factors are: Change in Sense, Presence of two or more senses, Change in reference, and Felicitous change in sense.

A. Change in Sense.

Change in sense, i.e., change in mode of presentation, means exposing the presenting structure of a sign to external influences. A sentence such as 'I need them here' has the first sense to the hearer based on shared knowledge of semantic rules as a statement which has propositional content (verbal action) stating subject's 'need of the object them'. Its force is that it asserts the subject's state of needing the object them here. Its reference points to the subject requirement of the object them at a particular location here.

The second sense is on the function of the statement such as requests, or commands to a verbal action of the propositional content. It may be done by stating an assertion 'I need them here' with an angry, sadness,

or even a happiness emotive force causing propositional content to ‘be measured as’, ‘be causing’, or ‘be deserving’ an emotional facial expression used in speaking it, as seen in an utterance ‘Sir, you are standing on my foot’ in chapter 2.3. The change in an emotive force, affects the first sense that is in the grammatical structure by shifting focus of an utterance from the speaker’s mere assertion of ‘statement of requiring the object to be at the subject location’ to ‘an emotive function attached to an utterance’ which measures a verbal action as forced by an emotive force. The change in sense of a sign/utterance due to introduction of an emotive force is what is the focus of discussion in the entire third chapter.

B. The presence of two or more senses in the sentence.

When the grammatical structure of a sentence has two senses, the function and intention of propositional content may as well have two senses and two references (two truth values). For example, if an assertive utterance ‘Your house is on fire’ is propositionally true according to truth conditions, it has the first sense to the hearer based on shared knowledge of grammatical rules as a statement which has propositional content (verbal action) where the speaker’s statement has a propositional force which ‘supply information to the object about focusing on his/her house being on fire’. The second sense is on the effects of the first propositional force, i.e., how the object of the sentence uses the supplied information, if the supplied information is used by the hearer/object to perform an immediate action, then that supplied information is not only thought to have a propositional force of assertion but also direction. In other words, the sentence serves as ‘an assertion’, and as ‘a directive’, because, it has two direct propositional forces which the sense of the first propositional force produces, and a second sense with a directive propositional force. The speaker may still choose to add the third indirect sense with its own propositional force by introducing an emotive force such as saying, ‘Your house is on fire’ with a happiness facial expression to add information on the spoken utterance ‘to be measured as happy’, ‘causing happiness’, or ‘deserving happiness’ which may serve a Schadenfreude function, that has an intention to laugh at hearer’s misfortunes. In these three propositional forces, two are directly stated in the sentence and one is emotionally signified with a happiness emotive force, and they are all thought to be having three different references, as figures of meanings.

C. Change in reference.

Change in sense means change in mode of presentation which also means exposing the presenting structure of a sign/sentence to external influence which may be done by introducing a 'force' to a 'sense' and that this 'force' means a propositional force, which can be 'force of assertion', 'force of questioning for response', 'force of direction', and or 'an indirect emotive force of signification' leading to multiple references of a sign/sentence and thus creating newer functions and intentions.

On the other hand, change in reference may as well lead to change in function and intention of a sign/sentence. Change in reference means change in truth value of a sign/sentence/utterance. Truth values (reference) of a sentence is the quality of being 'true or false'. This may mean one of three things, first, change from true to false, second, change from false to true, third, change in truth by means of degrees, and fourth, change in falsity by means of degrees. Change in truth value of each 'sense' present in a sentence may be assessed by observing its success or failure to perform the speaker's intended function in the same interlocution act. If an utterance discussed above in B about Presence of two senses in one sentence, 'Your house is on fire' is false at the targeted hearer's side (not to be confused with over hearers), then it's first sense of an assertion propositional force and second sense of direction propositional force are both lacking references. i.e., they change from 'true reference at the speaker's side' into 'false reference at the hearer's side'. Introducing a third sense with a newer propositional force, by means of introducing an emotive force with happiness facial expressions, is still leading to 'change in degree of truth of reference at the speaker's side', that is, to laugh at other's misfortune into 'change into truth of reference at the hearer's side', that is, to laugh at the hearer's action of perceiving a wrong reference of his/her house being on fire.

D. Felicitous change in sense.

Felicity conditions are a set of four criteria supporting the success of a speech act, which are Propositional content, i.e., Speaker's awareness of a verbal action/state being able to be done. Preparatory condition, i.e., appropriate circumstance such as a setting for an action to be successful. Sincerity condition, i.e., seriousness, sincere or firm acknowledgement of an action to be done. And Essential condition, i.e., speaker's firm intention for an action to be successful. Therefore, truth conditions (truth or falsity) of a propositional force leads to change in reference of a speech act, which may also lead to change in function

or degree of function due to change in degree of truth value of an intended function of the speaker in part B and C in this series.

Yet, Felicitous change in sense, involves change in mode of presentation of a proposition by exposing the presenting structure of a sign/utterance's felicity conditions to external influence. This felicitous influence affecting sense of a sentence may be by, missing a felicity condition (absence of a felicity condition) to an intended sense, doubling of felicity conditions, or exceeding the scope of any of the felicity conditions.

When an utterance misses a felicity condition, a new sense different from the first direct sense arises, it may be an irony, metaphor, or insinuation. for instance, when an utterance, 'Sir, you are standing on my foot', misses the first felicity condition, i.e., propositional content, such as when 'Sir' is not standing on the speaker's foot (and both Speaker and Sir know it), it indicates Speaker's awareness of a verbal action/state 'not being able to be to be done'. And the question is why and what function is the speaker intending (what sense).

When it misses the second felicity condition, i.e., preparatory condition, such as when there are inappropriate circumstances such as when the speaker speaks it to 'Sir' who is far away from him, or in a phone conversation and they both (Speaker and Sir) know it, it indicates Speaker's awareness of a verbal action/state 'not being able to be to be done'. And the question is why and what function is the speaker intending (what sense).

When it misses the third felicity condition, i.e., sincerity condition, such as by introduction of an emotive force, such as when the speaker is not serious, not sincere or introduces an emotive force which opposes or contradicts with a propositional force primarily and directly intended, an emotive force may lead to two scenarios, first, it violates felicity conditions and second, it adds a newer sense and affect speakers' degree of performance of a speech act. In both scenarios, an emotive force violates felicity conditions, and an emotive force introduces a new sense to a speech act by affecting the degree of performance of a speech act. When an emotive force violates the felicity conditions of a speech act it is semiotically creating a totally new 'sense and reference' to mean different meanings such as irony. The question is why and what other function and intention may be intended by an emotive force.

An Emotive force.

An emotive force applied when there is an interplay between linguistic, extralinguistic and para-linguistic features to present a different meaning of a language unit such as a word or an utterance may be semantically recognizable and pragmatically distinguishable. Semantic recognition is revealed in the sense that an emotional speech act forms an independent construal label with independent conceptual perspective, and Pragmatic distinction is on the ability to signify a variety of intended meanings, functions, and intentions through mismatches between a facial expression, voice, and an utterance.

Extra-lingual features accompanying emotional utterances related messages include the human voice aspects such as loudness, energy, tone, pitch, intonation, and tone intensity. Para lingual features accompanying emotional utterances include aspects of facial emotional categories such as changes, movements, and intensity of facial features during interlocution. In both spoken and written languages, words may be used denotatively in naming emotions, triggering emotional ends, describing the occurrence and states of emotions, or describing the cause of an emotion.

Thus, an emotional word can be defined as any word which names an emotion (e.g., happy), triggers emotional effects (e.g., congratulations), describes presence and state of an emotion (e.g., laughing), or describes occurrence of an emotion trigger (e.g., Poverty).

Based on the definition of an emotional word, emotional words may thus be categorized into three types as follows.

- A. Denotative emotional words E.g., Happy, Sadness, Fear, Pride, Anger Etc.
- B. Trigger emotional words. E.g., Congratulation! Hey! Sorry! Etc.
- C. Affective emotional words. E.g., Wow, laughing, Crying, Shining, suicide, murder, Money Etc.

Language emotional meanings, functions, and intentions can be interpreted by the hearer based on an emotive force, sense and reference of individual emotional words and utterances. In this aspect an emotional utterance is semantically recognizable by its carriage of linguistic emotional message, emotional instructions, or emotional effects. In other words, an emotional utterance is an utterance which describes expression of one's emotion (e.g., She is happy), triggers the hearer's emotional reaction (e.g., congratulations John!), describes the occurrence of an emotion (e.g., Janeth is crying), or describes

occurrence of an emotion trigger (e.g., there is absolute poverty in Africa where innocent people spend under one US dollar a day!).

Emotional signification may be examined based on paralinguistic features of communication which can be voluntary or involuntary, and false or correct. It integrates linguistic and paralinguistic features in a triadic way, namely ‘sign, signifier, and signified.’

Starting with inquisition of accompanying facial expressions for emotional signification, for instance, a human face may be regarded as an independent sign (index) which refers or represent a meaningful sensation such as discomfort, comfort, distaste, or unsettledness and which has an ideal concept in a language dictionary such as Anger, Happiness, Joy, Pain, or Sadness.

Under similar grounds the same sign (facial expression or word/utterance) may refer to a particular meaningful sensation such as discomfort while denoting different ideal concepts such as disgust and sadness. The following table 3.1 shows the three aspects of an emotional facial expression index/sign.

Table 3:1 Three aspects of an emotional index

SIGN (Word/Utterance), INDEX (Facial expression)	SIGNIFIER (what is neurologically felt and sometimes recognized by hearers)	SIGNIFIED (Ideal Concept)
Facial expression & or Utterance	Discomfort	Disgust
Facial expression & or Utterance	Discomfort	Sadness

What is named in the dictionary as an emotion name e.g., Disgust, is the ideal concept that is linguistically recognizable (Signified) and what is felt inside the human body is the sensation itself (signifier), and the two which are shown on speaker’s facial expression and or spoken as an utterance i.e., which can be voluntary or involuntary based on an emotional utterance (trigger) intensity and/or speaker’s pragmatic functions and intention are together forming a sign/index expression.

Therefore, in emotional signification i.e., attempts to condition meaning making processes the ‘Signifier’ may have multiple ‘Signified’ with voluntary or involuntary facial expressions where an involuntary facial expression appears to be correct by virtue of it being involuntary, and a voluntary facial expression depends on the speaker pragmatic intentions. On the other hand, the ability and inability to hide or mask facial expressions based on voluntary aspects of facial features for effective emotional signification may be a key skill in developing emotional language pragmatic competence.

To understand mechanisms for Emotional signification (meaning making processes) in human language there is a need to observe three angles of interpreting linguistic emotional meanings, functions, and intentions, namely: The Speaker’s angle, The Hearer’s angle, and the Reader’s angle as shown in Table 3.2, Table 3.3, and Table 3.4 respectively. In these three angles a linguistic emotional message passes through four phases: ‘Trigger, Sensation, Signification (Brain neuro-interpretation and language faculty processing) and Expression (word/utterance & or facial expression)’.

Table 3:2The speaker’s angle: Speaker's mechanisms of emotional signification.

TRIGGER (Trigger)	SENSATION (Signifier)	SIGNIFICATION (Signified)	EXPRESSION (Sign/Index)
An object’s, speaker’s effects. E.g., -A Razor cut stimulus. -An utterance ‘If I were you, I’d leave him straight away’.	Pain. (The brain interprets the stimulus)	Neuroscience performance and communication with language faculty. (The choice to lie, mask, hide or show the inner truth)	A Spoken word/utterance and Facial expression. E.g., Oh! Really! And, Or facial expression. (False or correct facial expression, voluntary, or involuntary facial expression)

Table 3:3 The hearer's angle: Hearer's mechanisms of emotional signification.

TRIGGER (Trigger)	SENSATION (Signifier)	SIGNIFICATION (Signified)	EXPRESSION (Sign/Index)
<p>An ideal concept expressed by another speaker. i.e., A word and, or its accompanied facial expression. E.g., A complement (Congratulations!)</p>	<p>Comfort, victory, or Harmony The brain Interprets an utterance. The brain interprets a stimulus</p>	<p>Neuroscience performance and communication with language faculty. (The choice to lie, mask, hide or show the inner truth)</p>	<p>A Spoken word/utterance and Facial expression E.g., Thank you + happy facial expression. (False or correct facial expression, voluntary, or involuntary facial expression)</p>

Table 3:4 The reader's angle: Reader's mechanisms of emotional signification.

TRIGGER (Trigger)	SENSATION (Signifier)	SIGNIFICATION (Signified)	EXPRESSION (Sign/Index)
<p>A written sentence E.g., A complement (Congratulations!)</p>	<p>[Discomforts]</p>	<p>Neuroscience performance and communication with language faculty. E.g., Shock</p>	<p>Facial expression and or word/utterance. E.g., Wow! & Or Facial expression (False or correct facial expression, voluntary, or</p>

			involuntary facial expression)
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The above three Tables (The Speaker's, The Hearer's, and the Reader's) suggest a four phases mechanism for a complete Emotional signification process, which includes four phases, namely: 'Trigger, Sensation, Signification, and Expression'. The choice for accompanied facial expressions in phase four i.e., expression, begins in phase three i.e., signification where phase two i.e., emotional sensations are interpreted as voluntary and, or involuntary and the message is agreed with the language faculty on what to express as a sign/an index on face (true facial expressions, false facial expressions, hiding facial expression, or masking facial expressions), what to speak with the mouth i.e., an utterance, and how to organize the sounds of the word/utterance being spoken i.e., prosody.

For involuntary sensation, there are weak involuntary sensation and strong involuntary sensation. They both have direct reference to facial features neurons, whereby, sometimes despite the agreement with the brain language faculty to mask or hide the felt emotional sensations they are still expressed and understood by the viewer/hearer in both the third and fourth phases. The ability to have a complete understanding of meaning making processes(signification) between emotion neurons and language faculty in the brain may be a key indicator of a skill toward emotional language pragmatic competence, to both liars (speakers), and lie-detectors (hearers).

There seems to be a connection between 'stimulus-to-sensation neural networks' and 'language faculty management of facial expressions', the stronger emotional utterances are, the harder it is for a person to mask their sensations. This hints on emotional utterance facial expressions whether true or false, masked or hidden, is decided in phase three (signification). In this regard it is instantly possible to recognize unstimulated emotional facial expression e.g. When a speaker shows a sudden false angry facial expression with no phase one that is the trigger basis. In this aspect the speaker is thought to have expressed unsensed facial expression of a sensible emotion. A language user cannot show an angry facial expression and be understood as angry if there is no anger trigger. Thus, in context where a speaker approaches a hearer and says 'Congratulations!' using a 'happy facial expression', without any basic reason for a congratulation

wish, then such an utterance suggests for pragmatic miss-formedness, pragmatic implication, or a presupposition. In similar circumstances if a speaker says ‘congratulations!’ with a ‘sad facial expression’, since ‘a congratulation wish’ is usually pragmatically accompanied with a happiness related expression which is opposite to sadness expression, the speaker is therefore thought to be presupposing based on an unknown trigger basis or he/she is pragmatically implying or referencing (reference as a component of meaning) something else.

In a rather traditional way, language users tend to create reference of emotional expressions (reference as one of the three components of meaning) with certain inner sensations where they speak and listen while referring specific emotional expressions/propositional force with their counterpart sensations rather than others, for instance, referring ‘Anger’ to ‘Pain’ rather than ‘Pleasure’. This reference of inner sensations with emotional facial expressions is what links the second emotional signification phase i.e., Sensation to the fourth emotional signification phase i.e., expression.

‘Sensations’ which are referring to ‘Facial expressions’ are pragmatically reliable in distinguishing the sign i.e., facial expression/utterance given as a reference of a ‘state of mind’ where encoding and decoding with emotional facial expressions makes interpretation of such emotional facial indexes the comments deriving and depicting their perception toward the proposition force stated as a trigger. i.e., Facial expressions can be a measure, cause, and deserving referent of proposition force of the speaker to the hearer. Thus, a propositional force of an emotive force of a facial expression is referred as ‘being measured as’, ‘being causing’, or ‘being deserving’ propositional content verbal action or state. Table 3.5. below shows the reference (component of meaning) of expressions to sensations experienced in interlocution involving emotional facial expressions.

Table 3:5The reference of facial expressions to sensations.

Sensations	Expressions
Pleasure, Warmth	Happy face
Pain, Irritation, Stress	Angry face

Offenses, Revulsion, Repulsion	Disgust face
Pain, sorrow, inferiority, loneliness	Sad face
Shock	Fear face
Newness	Surprised face
Pain, cold	Contempt face

The reference of facial expressions to sensation begins after the baby is born. The baby is exposed to usual and unusual sensations which are then categorized reversibly such as expected from unexpected affects and pleasant from unpleasant affects, which conditions facial muscles with culture based acquired sensible samples.

Thus, when the baby has acquired the art of emotional expression, probably in the third week after birth, expression turn into two categories, the voluntary and involuntary emotional facial expressions. Voluntary emotional expressions are generated as a reaction in a reversible mode where the baby is forced by the brain to give facial comments to sensitive affects in any of the two opposite affects in polarity of emotional expressions (e.g., desirable against undesirable, or expected against unexpected). This is why when an adult shows the baby any of the desirable, expected, wished, or pleasant child plays, the baby comments by laughing, smiling, wondering, or even crying and showing anger through the face.

The facial comments to a particular stimulation may be associated with cultural values about the trigger (phase one of emotional signification) in different degree such as being slightly pleasant, very pleasant, or unpleasant. Other factors may be social linguistic i.e., Age, Gender, Personality, and Race. A baby develops individual perceptual abilities which governs the judgement of reaction to give out through facial expression to different affects such as expected, unexpected, desirable, undesirable, pleasant etc.,

The symbolic nature of facial expressions and words.

There is a challenge in observing the property of language as ‘symbolic’ in the system of language, that is on whether the symbolic nature in the system of language means only ‘words’ ‘rather’ than ‘face’ and or ‘voice’, which happens when all the three are used at the same time in an act of speaking and seem not to symbolize the same proposition. If the language property ‘symbolic’ and the word ‘symbol/sign’ in the system of language means mere words, then the question is why do faces mean otherwise? Why do voices mean otherwise? Do words, face and voice need to align for the so-called ‘oral language’ to be symbolic and mean the same thing in the system of language? If not, are faces and voices not symbolic, and why can’t facial expressions and voice be observed as symbols (indexes) at the growing semantic and syntactic levels, as it is the case for words as symbols at the surface structure involving low to high levels of meaning namely, morpheme level, word level, phrasal level, clause level, and sentence level, do the face and voices symbolic nature change as they grow into high levels?

Such a challenge adds to an approach on viewing emotional signification as a semiotic process. The symbols involved are three, the word as a symbol, the face as a symbol (index) and the voice as a symbol. Looking on vagueness of myriad facial expressions deviating pragmatic meanings of an emotional utterance, it brings to light that the ‘face’ as a unique symbolic mode of emotional signification competes with ‘words’ given their symbolic and conventional nature.

A facial expression appears to be a dynamic index of meaningful linguistic emotional propositions of human being’s state of mind. A facial expression is related to an utterance in the way that it is ‘a measure’, ‘effect’, and or ‘deserving mode of presentation’ of the proposed contents.

This indexical symbol does signify emotional meanings and functions. For instance, voluntary emotional facial expressions such as ‘a teacher's serious facial reprimand to a noisy classroom’ and Involuntary emotional facial expressions such as ‘a razor cut stimulated sadness facial expression’ reveals varied nuances of emotional senses with different emotive triggers.

3.2 Emotional Signification as a Pragmatic Act.

In chapter 2.3 and chapter 3.1, I've described how an emotive force can affect 'sense' of a sentence as one of the three components of meaning leading to 'replacement of reference', or 'introduction of a newer degree of reference' which leads to change in function and intention of a propositional force or speech act. The following observations show how an emotive force present in an emotional facial expression makes emotional signification (interplay and or mismatches of utterance, facial expression, and voice) a pragmatic/speech act.

3.2.1 Emotional Signification Speech Act at the Speaker's Side.

A Speech act of an utterance is defined in terms of; (1) Speaker's intention i.e., expectation to perform specific function, and (2) Perlocutionary effects i.e., functional results of an utterance which matches speaker's specific intention.

Just as utterances, an emotive force of facial expressions may be signified with; (1) Speaker's intention i.e., expectation to perform specific function, and (2) Perlocutionary effects i.e., functional results of an utterance which matches speaker's specific intention.

Observe the following sets with seven labels 'X, Y, Z, Z (1,2,3...7), HH, HH (1,2,3...7), and PH'

X stands for an utterance i.e., Come here.

Y for voice aspects i.e., neutral utterance-based emotional expressions.

Z for neutral utterance-based facial expression emotion where a person feels an utterance-based emotion as a signifier.

Z (1,2,3...7) for one of facial expressions signified with an emotive force other than neutral emotional facial expression.

HH for normal intended meanings of an utterance proposition force.

HH (1,2, 3...7) for one of emotionally signified change in functions/intentions due to introduction of an emotive force, and

PH for meanings (functions/intentions) affected by a lingual utterance (**X**).

Primary meaning means ‘a meaning of an utterance surface structure-based propositional force’.

Secondary meaning means ‘a meaning of facial expression-based propositional/emotive force’.

If a set (X+Y+Z) in example 1 below intends HH and only HH (Primary intended meaning due to sentence-based propositional force present in utterance X) where X (propositional force 1-Neutral) intends the first H in HH (function 1-Informing to come).

1. Come here

Then, a set (X+Y+Z1) in utterance 2 below intends HH1 where Z1 intends H1 in HH1 (Secondary meaning due to change in function introduced by an emotive force present in face Z1) where Z1(emotive force 1-Angry) intends H1 (function 2-Commanding to come).

2. Come here (With a neutral tone and an angry face)

And a set (X+Y+Z2) in utterance 3 below intends HH2 where Z2 intends H2 in HH2 (Secondary meaning due to change in function introduced by an emotive force present in face Z2) where Z2 (emotive force 2-contempt) intends H2 (function 3-Contemptuous pleading to come/begging to come).

3. Come here (With a neutral tone and contempt face)

Where a set (X1+Y+Z) in utterance 4 below intends P1H where X1 intends P1 in P1H (Primary meaning due to sentence-based propositional force present in utterance X1) where X1 (propositional force 2-Neutral) intends P (function 4-Requesting to come).

4. Come here right now

Whereby a set (X2+Y+Z) in utterance 5 below intends P2H where X2 intends P2 in P2H (Primary meaning due to sentence-based propositional force present in utterance X2) where X2 (propositional force 2-Neutral) intends P2 (function 5-Requesting to come).

5. Would you come here please!

And a set (X2+Y+Z1) in utterance 6 below intends P2H1 where X2 intends P2 and Z1 intends H1 in P2H1. (Both primary and secondary meanings due to sentence-based propositional force present in utterance X2,

and facial expression-based emotive force present in Z1) where X2 (propositional force 2-Neutral) intends P2 (function 5-Requesting to come), and Z1 (emotive force 1-angry) intends H1 in P2H1 (function 6-Commanding to come).

Note that utterance 6, has two functions, the primary function is due to the nature of an utterance as a 'directive-request' and the secondary function is due to the nature of facial expression as an emotive angry force as a 'directive-command', in this set two directives manifests two contradicting aspects, which are 'a request in conflict with a command'.

6. Would you come here please! (With a neutral tone and angry facial expressions).

Then, $X+Y+(Z1, Z2, Z3...Z7)$ are Emotional significations speech acts by virtue of their emotive forces' functions and intentions where change in Z- factors affect change in H-factors and change in X-factors affect change in P-factors, Change in Y-factors (prosody) are perpendicular to changes in Z-factors (facial expressions) as they both play the same emotional roles.

And $(X1, X2, X3...X7+(Y+Z))$ are speech acts by virtue of propositional forces functions/intentions where change in X- factors replaces one of H factor with P factors in a HH set.

The above empirical derivations show that facial expressions are acts intending to show the speaker's emotive force which may have 'opposite or another degree of references', as compared to reference/denotation of utterances without influence of emotional facial expressions or voice. They might be commands, orders, requests, instructions, warning, directions, insults, jokes, promises, greetings, apologies, thanksgiving, or functional expressive speech acts of the user's state of mind. i.e., what is meant, performed and or intended when speakers involve 'emotive force' through emotional facial expressions.

The problem with 'emotive forces' at the speaker's side is that they may be opposite, matching, or mismatching 'utterance propositional force' to indicate or perform different functions and intentions.

For instance, the following five groups of utterances have verbal actions and states 'directly stated' in their 'propositional force' but their accompanying 'emotive forces' are indirectly contradicting with them.

1. Group one

Come here (with an angry facial expression).

Come here (with a coward/sad facial expression).

2. Group two

I've finally found you (with a happy facial expression)

I've finally found you (with an angry facial expression)

3. Group 3

You are an idiot (with a happy facial expression)

You are an idiot (with an angry facial expression)

4. Group 4

I'm so sad for your loss (with a happy facial expression)

I'm so sad for your loss (with a sad facial expression)

I'm so sad for your loss (with a disgust facial expression)

5. Group 5

I'm so happy you have won the prize (with a disgust facial expression).

I'm so happy you have won the prize (with a sad facial expression)

I'm so happy you have won the prize (with a contempt facial expression)

3.2.2 Emotional Signification Speech Act at the Hearer's Side.

Facial expressions may also stand alone to function as independent facial expressions speech acts. E.g., Still, and muted or motion pictures and emojis. Deciphering such facial expressions emotive forces guides the viewing of interlocutors or passers-by to derive a conclusion that a particular facial image may be performing a warning facial act interpreted as 'Stop photographing me!', a requesting facial act interpreted as 'again', or performing a commissive speech act based on the request asked in a directive speech act.

Emotional signification speech acts at the hearer's side as response to Sentence-based triggers.

For instance, in the most nostalgic moments of human lives, language users may be in need to express or respond to questions from those in relationship with them. The facial expressions they display as responses

when encountering such situations or questions are pragmatically distinguishable by virtue of their emotive force ‘to complete performance of actions’, ‘stop performance of actions’, ‘trigger performance of actions’ and or ‘deviate/distract performance of actions’.

Consider the following facial expressions in speaker B brackets expressed as responses to their specific situations and their signified facial acts in the right context.

1. Speaker A: Will you marry me?

Speaker B; (A sudden open happiness/smile facial expression). – ‘Accepting’ speech act.

2. Speaker A; (Stares at a person for a while)

Speaker B; (A sudden angry facial expression). – ‘Warning’ speech act.

3. Speaker A: You are fired!

Speaker B; (A sudden sadness facial expression). – ‘Blaming’ speech act.

4. Speaker A; (Spies on speaker B with binoculars through the window).

Speaker B; (A sudden disgust facial expression) – ‘Blaming’, ‘Insulting’ speech act.

5. Speaker A: (In a silent classroom, student ‘A’ laughs out loud, the teacher turns around to see who it is). – ‘Questioning’ speech act.

Speaker B: (the entire classroom turns around to look at speaker ‘A’). – ‘Reporting/Directing’ speech act.

However, Speaker B’s response in the above five speech scenarios when sensed from ‘wrong triggers’, ‘wrong emotive force’ and ‘wrong felicity conditions’ tend to signify otherwise, more, or less than intended because of an act of speaking of ‘triggers intended states of minds’ in form of propositions. As observed in the beginning of section 3.1 about ‘four factors accountable for change in meaning of a sign/sentence/utterance’ which may lead to change in functions and intentions in both direct and indirect ways which are, Change in Sense, Presence of two or more senses, Change in reference, and Felicitous change in sense, and concluded with a finding about an emotive force that, there are two scenarios, that, an emotive force violates felicity conditions, and, an emotive force introduces a new sense to a speech act by affecting the degree of performance of a speech act and that when an emotive force violates felicity

conditions of a speech act it is semiotically creating a totally new ‘sense and reference’ meaning different meanings such as irony which lead to the question why and what other functions and intentions are intended by an emotive force.

Due to what may be privacy concerns and ethical limitations to empirical research works, the researcher could not find available online real-life speech datasets and corpus showing matches and mismatches of emotion expressions with linguistic contents of an utterance. The only available online datasets and corpus are recorded television series, movies, and acted speech, conversations, and dialogues. For example, the Ryerson Audio-Visual Database of Emotional Speech and Song (RAVDESS) in Livingstone and Russo (2018) contains utterances of different emotional manifestations performing different speech acts. Another dataset is the Friends Corpus presented by Chen and Choi (2016) which contains a collection of all the conversations that occurred over 10 seasons of Friends, a popular American TV series that ran in the 1990s. Across the 10 seasons there are 236 episodes, 3,107 scenes (conversations), 67,373 utterances, and 700 characters (users).

However, the following observations show analysis of the influence of ‘wrong triggers’, ‘wrong emotive force’ and ‘wrong felicity conditions’ to the failure of speaker B response function (Functional failure of respondent’s facial expression act).

For instance, when the 2021 U.S. Open women’s singles champion was playing in London at Royal Albert Hall, 7 years old tennis fan Leo Gomez-Franqueira shouting a proposition trigger ‘Emma, would you marry me?’ The response facial expression act by a Tennis player Emma Raducanu with ‘a brief sudden flash of a smile/happiness facial expression’ toward the first speaker does not meet the status of ‘Accepting- emotional facial act’ as it is the case in example 1 above, because of ‘wrong felicity conditions’ which falsifies the trigger despite having ‘propositional force’ and ‘emotive force’ of an utterance by both speakers, Emma, and Leo.

Felicity conditions are a set of four criteria supporting the success of a speech act, their failure leading to failure of Emma’s happiness facial expression act as ‘an accepting act’ are,

The first, an error in propositional content, i.e., Both speakers are aware of a verbal action/state in Leo’s utterance and Emma’s happiness emotive force as ‘not being able to be to be done’ and thus ‘not deserving’

because of western social cultural differences such as legal marriage proposal age, and age difference factor.

The second, is an error in preparatory condition, i.e., inappropriate circumstance such as settings for an action to be successful where distance between the two and overhearers blockage of a required close distance as a Western cultural norm of operation of marriage proposal makes a happiness emotive force 'not deserving' in both verbal actions/states expressed in Leo's utterance and Emma's happiness facial act.

The third, is an error in sincerity condition, i.e., unseriousness, insincerity and Leo's lack of firm acknowledgement of an action to be done, based on Leo's immediate 'shift in focus' from the respondent hearer (Emma) to overhearers (tennis match fans) 'before and after' his 'proposition force' is answered. This 'shift in focus from 'a primary propositional force' affects an utterance's intended function because of introducing 'a secondary new emotive force' that contradicts with 'a primary propositional force' leading to change in sense of the directive utterance 'Emma would you marry me?' and thus making a new sense accountable for 'change in reference of a propositional force', a case discussed in the beginning of section 3.1 about four factors accountable for change in meaning of a sign/sentence/utterance which may lead to change in functions/intentions.

And the fourth, is an error in essential condition, i.e., The speaker 'Leo' has no firm intention for an action to be successful, simply because of introducing 'a newer emotive force' causing 'shifting in focus' and 'change in truth value' of a primary propositional force resulting into 'deviation in reference of an utterance expression' and finally leading to 'change in function', the primary function based on Leo's utterance is 'proposing for marriage' and the final function created by Leo is 'joking'.

Emotional signification speech acts at the hearer's side as response to situation-based triggers.

There are times when an emotive force of a facial expression is directly referencing 'state of mind' as response to different situations and get understood as stated without involving utterances/words as in the following four cases.

1. An angry facial expression given back as a response to a privacy invading strange photographer.

This may depict the photographer's action as a trigger, and the respondent's facial expression as a facial expression act. The relationship between sociolinguistic status of a trigger against sociolinguistic status of expression, is on their 'references' as a component of meaning, which when the trigger's reference is culturally or semiotically different between the 'trigger source' and 'respondent', it leads to 'sociolinguistic misinterpretation' by the expressor who gives back phase four of an expression intending functions which are not expected by the source of the trigger. Difference in cultural, semiotic, and sociolinguistic perception of a trigger between the speaker and hearer may thus lead to misunderstanding of an emotive force 'as measured as', 'as causing', or 'as deserving' the trigger's referent expression and thus affecting communication. In such cases, if trigger X is semiotically perceived by the speaker/trigger source 'as deserving' response expression Z (Facial expression Z). But contrary to that, the same trigger X obtains other response expressions Z1, Z2, Z3...Z7. It may mean that sensation of trigger X obtains response expressions Z1, Z2, Z3...Z7 because of differences in signification processing between the Speaker's trigger and the hearer's expression. In this case, the hearer is thought to have misinterpreted first speaker's trigger X, if and only if the reversion of the same emotional signification remains constant/renders response expression Z (Facial expression Z). i.e., If the same thing can be done to the source e.g., strange privacy invading photographer trigger under similar circumstances and still renders response expression Z and only Z, rather than Z1, Z2, Z3...Z7.

2. A teacher's serious facial expression given back as a reprimand to a noisy class, and A disgust facial expression given back as a response to a crying child.
3. Any facial expression given back as response to a written sentence such as a sentence 'You are fired!'.
4. Any overhearer's facial expression expressed as a reaction to an overheard utterance such as an utterance 'They were aware of the boring, hurting and meaningless programs like that'.

3.2.3 Emotional Signification as a Speech Act and its Distractions.

As shown in figure 3.1 below, emotional signification as a speech act may have distractions leading to 'change or deviation in reference' as a component of meaning and thus affecting its function/intention. An emotional index/expression may represent multiple meaningful sensations/signifiers which are

pragmatically distinguishable i.e., contains multiple signified intentions but their ‘references’ gets confused and misinterpreted by expressing them ‘as measured as’, ‘as causing’ and ‘as deserving’ the same sensation/signifier. Below is the list of distractions after each of the four phases, the distraction after phase four may lead to an emotional signification error. In the final component of figure 3.1, the term ‘meaning’ is divided into ‘function’ and ‘intention’ as two distinct parts because of possibility for ‘unconscious functions/unintended functions’ performed in emotional signification which make the primary intention of the speaker getting emotionally signified (recognized) by the hearer different from the primary function as consciously/intentionally conditioned by the trigger source, or as an emotional signification error.

Distraction after phase 1.

This distraction is in two scenarios,

- a. The hearer grasps the trigger as it is formulated by the trigger source/speaker. i.e., with the same action, same utterance surface structure, same facial expression, and same voice, but senses different ‘sensation’ which creates a new mode of presentation of ‘sense’ affecting ‘reference’ intended by the trigger source. E.g., an example of a privacy invading strange photographer. This kind of distraction is a ‘constructive distraction.’
- b. The trigger source/speaker knowingly or unknowingly fails to observe felicity conditions and or emotive forces though he/she uses an appropriate sentence surface structure. This kind of distraction is ‘a destructive distraction’ because it tends to violate emotive forces and sincerity conditions of a propositional force of verbal action/state of the sentence propositional content which creates ‘newer sense of meaning’ with ‘a newer reference of meaning’ which perform a secondary function. For example, an utterance in section 3.2.2 by Leo presents a surface structure of an utterance ‘Emma would you marry me?’ with a destructive distraction to perform an indirect meaning. Unobserved felicity conditions such as shift in focus and insufficient felicity conditions are the cause of destructive distractions after the trigger.

Distraction after phase 2.

In this category the hearer grasps the ‘trigger’ and its ‘sensation’ but acquires a different ‘reference’ which affects ‘signification’ that’s the search for meaning in his/her schema creates an opposite or different

reference as a basis for a new response expression trigger not intended by the first trigger source unconsciously (constructive distraction). In this phase the respondent performs a distraction out of 'ignorance of the conditioned intention' from the trigger source which causes failure to grasp the third phase that is signification and thus giving a distraction to the first distractor, the first source signification. It may be due to the difference between speaker and hearer in understanding an emotive force (Constructive distraction) or degree of knowledge of a distraction due to social linguistic perception of an applied emotional utterance. For example, using different emotive forces in speaking utterances which may change direct meanings into indirect meanings to the hearer despite firm intention by the second speaker to speak an utterance meaning as the surface structure proposes, such as emotively responding by saying 'I do', or 'If I were you, I'd leave him straight away'.

Distractions after phase 3.

Distraction after phase three happens when the hearer grasps the trigger, sensation, and signification as conditioned by the trigger source/speaker but creates another 'signification' not intended by the trigger source/speaker by expressing wrong 'expression' to mask or hide his 'state of mind' as a reaction to the trigger. This happens when a signified utterance has two contradicting senses and references when accompanied with an emotive force, but the hearer chooses to respond to one that is not intended by the speaker (constructive distraction).

(The difference between Distractions after phase 3 and Distractions after phase 2 is 'ignorance and knowledge', whereby, in distraction after phase 2, the respondent is not intending to deviate the conditioned/signified intention of the trigger source but performs a distraction out of ignorance of the first conditioned intention from the trigger source which causes failure to grasp the third phase that is signification. But in distraction after phase 3, the respondent seeks to deviate the conditioned intention of the trigger source after recognizing the speaker's intention. The basis for a distinction between distractions after phase 2 and distractions after phase 3 is the third phase i.e., signification)

In distractions after phase 3, both the first speaker and the hearer are aware that the hearer is trying to deviate from the trigger. For instance, speaker 1(b) utterance surface structure changes references based

on an accompanying emotive force, speaker 1(a) responds to 1(b) as a distraction deviating from a complaining function by speaker 1(b).

1(a) Do you accept working here?

1(b) I do. (Angry emotion category instead of neutral emotion category). To perform an act of complaining instead of an oath.

1(a) You are warmly welcome. (Constructive distraction)

Or

1(a) The contract will be signed on Monday (Destructive distraction)

On the other hand, When the hearer switches to a new topic that is not related to utterance surface structure propositional force or uses an utterance emotive force that creates the secondary intention, he/she is thought to be creating a destructive distraction. For instance, saying ‘The contract will be signed on Monday’ which ignores the complaining trigger in angry emotional signification of an utterance ‘I do’.

Distractions after phase 4.

At last, in distractions happening after phase four, expressions lead to ‘an emotional signification error’ as it is the case for unclear or pretended triggers i.e., absence of a ‘trigger’ where an emotional signification process is forced to start at the second phase ‘sensation’ as it is the case for a ‘congratulation’ wish without a reason and intention for its expression toward the hearer’s angle.

The emotional signification error is a conditioning error seen by the hearer failure to accurately interpret the function of a signified emotional expression/utterance because of it being presupposing or implying a signified function not yet mentioned as shown in the utterance ‘congratulations’ in dialogue 1(a) and (b) below.

1(a) Congratulations! (With a surprised emotive force).

1(b) Why?

1(a) You left your house keys at the bar; it is twenty miles from here.

This is because what is on the face (expression) must reflect what is sensed (sensation) from the causative emotional utterance (trigger). But contrary to that, to create meaning (function/intention) by conditioning (emotional signification-conditioning), the speaker's interplay of facial expression and an utterance does not reflect any sensed background trigger and thus the speaker is thought/perceived by the listener to be creating a meaning different from the primary meaning and function that the surface structure would usually perform unless he/she ask for the second trigger as an explanation of the first trigger. The reasons for distractions after phase four which lead to hearer's emotional signification errors is evident in hearer's misinterpretation, speaker's misrepresentation, hearer's misperception, and hearer's neglect due to mismatches, semantic and cultural differences, or audio-visual impairment. Figure 3.1 below shows an overview of emotional signification as a speech act and its distractions.

Figure 3:1 Emotional signification as a speech act and its distractions.

3.2.4 Functional Transfiguration in Searle Taxonomy of Speech Acts.

Austin (1962a) defines a speech act as an illocutionary act performed with a certain force in uttering an utterance. He puts speech acts into five categories, 'verdictive', 'Exercitive', 'Commissive', 'Expositive', and 'Behabitive' as "a basis of discussion rather than as a set of established results", In Searle's words. Searle (1979, p. 8). Searle reached a conclusion on an alternative taxonomy of speech act after having

observed weaknesses in Austin's speech act taxonomy in Austin (1962a) to be, among other factors, 'Not classifying illocutionary acts but English illocutionary verbs' noting verbs like 'intend' to be clearly lacking 'intention' and hence not performative, where the surface structure of the word 'intend' does not have 'an intending performative force'. Another weakness Searle finds in Austin (1962a) taxonomy of speech acts is the 'lack of a basic principle' on which a speech acts is built on.

Searle's alternative taxonomy of speech act, as he argues, takes "an illocutionary point and its corollaries, and direction of fit and expressed sincerity conditions" as a basis for construction of his classification. The speech acts taxonomy he proposes includes, 'Assertion, which is built on belief', 'Directive, which is built on wish or desire', 'Commissive, which is built on intention', 'Expressive, which is built on psychological state, and 'Declaration, which is built on declarations.'

Each of Searle's category of speech acts is built on a unique goal-based propositional content namely, belief, wish or desire, intention, psychological state, or declaration. These goals are each built in a verbal action or state expressed in the propositional force. Propositional content is the verbal action or state implicitly or explicitly stated in the sentence and which (except for declarations) contains sincerity conditions. Influences on a goal may affect the nature of each of Searle's speech acts. For instance, introducing an emotive force to some utterances in categories of Searle's speech acts may transfigure a speech act goal by influencing the degree and, or changing its primary function due to change in goals that a speech act category is built on, namely belief, wish or desire, intention, psychological state, or declaration, resulting into a speech act retaining its surface structure while losing its goal which means change in function and meaning.

When an emotive force violates felicity conditions, a function of a speech act is also influenced but not destroyed since it may still perform other functions with primary goals of other categories of speech acts in the taxonomy. In this case, a speech act with a 'directive' surface structure may be having 'an expressive' goal when spoken with an emotive force. Also, a speech act with a 'directive speech act' may be having a new function determined with an emotive force.

Thus, apart from violating felicity conditions, an emotive force may also violate other pragmatic forces holding functional goals on which a speech act category is built on. Let's observe functional transfiguration

of speech act goals in each of Searle's category of speech acts which leads to violation of pragmatic forces and change in meaning and functions.

1. Functional transfiguration in assertive speech acts.

Proponents of normative accounts on categories of speech acts identify an assertive speech act category based on 'norm' that is the condition determining an assertive speech act category. An assertion is an utterance intending to commit the speaker (in varying degrees) to something being the case, to the truth of the expressed proposition. Assertions are assessable as true or false. What is common in all assertive utterances is 'words to world direction of fit' and 'a belief as its expressing psychological state'. Searle (1979). Assertive speech acts perform functions such as informing, showing, reporting, expressing, explaining etc., For example, 'That is my cow', 'John is a teacher', 'Honesty is the best policy', 'He is my best friend', or 'She likes eating'.

Belief as a goal of an assertion commits a speaker to a belief of something being the case. What an assertion does with an emotive force is molding a belief as a goal based on emotional categories. The difference in emotion categories generates substantial impacts to a propositional force performing an act. For instance, observe the change in a goal of an assertion by introduction of an emotive force as its performative force which assigns a new force to a propositional force to be 'as measured as', 'as causing', or 'as deserving' an emotive force.

1(a) He likes candies. (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Informing, Goal: Belief).

Sentence 1(a) is an assertion by virtue of it having 'a belief' of a verbal action. i.e., 'Him liking candies' as its goal. This belief-based goal has been used to perform the function of informing.

1(b) He likes candies. (Emotive force: Disgust, Function: Suggesting, Complaining, Goal: Desire).

1(c) He likes candies. (Emotive force: Surprised, Function: Questioning, Goal: Desire).

1(d) That is my gift. (Emotive force: Surprised, Function: Questioning, Goal: Desire).

Sentence 1(b) which is spoken with a disgust emotive force, has a primary surface structure of an assertion as it has a belief-based verbal action of the speaker stating 'Him liking candies' which is the primary goal,

yet when the language user hears it in a disgust emotive force and associate the verbal action of him liking candies to ‘be measured as’, ‘be causing’ or ‘be deserving’ disgust, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker’s mere information on his ‘belief’ but rather ‘speaker’s desire’ on ‘Suggesting’ or ‘complaining’ on a verbal action of ‘liking candies’ to ‘be causing’ disgust. This second information of a verbal action causing a specific emotional state is an implication that is indirectly stated with an emotive force to perform a function of ‘suggesting’ and ‘complaining’. It resembles with a feature of ‘wish and desire’ that is unique in a ‘Directive speech act’. Utterance 1(b) is thus thought to have undergone functional transfiguration from an assertion speech act in 1(a) to a Directive speech act with an assertive speech act surface structure in 1(b). Other forms of functional changes in assertive speech act surface structure are in utterance 1(c) and 1(d) above.

2. Functional transfiguration in Directive speech acts.

A directive is an utterance attempting (at different degrees) to get the hearer to do something. Directives are referred by Searle as Determinates of the determinable. What is common in all directive utterances is the ‘world to word direction of fit’ and ‘a wish/desire as a sincerity condition’. They perform functions such as asking, ordering, commanding, requesting, begging, pleading, praying, entreating, inviting, permitting, etc.

Sentence 2(a) and (b) show change in functions due to introduction of an emotive force. Note that, an emotive force is related to propositional force by assigning a new force to a propositional force to be ‘as measured as’, ‘as causing’, or ‘as deserving’ an emotive force.

2(a) Can you pass the salt? (Preparatory felicity condition: In the kitchen, Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Requesting, Goal: Desire).

2(b) Can you pass the salt? (Preparatory felicity condition: In the kitchen, Emotive force: Contempt, Function: Begging, Goal: Desire).

The differences emerging between 2(a) and 2(b) is the ‘shift of focus’ from 2(a) ‘requesting for completion of a verbal action/state’ i.e., the hearer’s response by passing the salt (as a primary function) which is at

the ending part 'pass the salt', to 2(b) 'begging for completion of a verbal action' by doubting for a speech act being able to be considered (Contempt). Note that, the stated verbal action' i.e., passing the salt, drops a primary function of 2(a) to a lower degree in 2(b) because of contempt suggesting that the speaker is doubting whether a speech act may be performed which makes it perform a secondary function of begging.

2(c) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Suggesting, Goal: Desire).

Sentence 2(c) is a 'directive speech act' by virtue of it having 'a desire' because of the speaker positioning oneself in a hearer's state and what verbal action to do i.e., 'leaving him straight away' as its goal. This desire-based goal has been used to perform a function of Suggesting.

2(d) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Emotive force: Angry, Function: Warning, Goal: Wish).

2(e) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Emotive force: Fear, Function: Advising, Goal: Wish).

Sentence 2(d) which is spoken with an angry emotive force, has a primary surface structure of a directive speech act as it has a desire-based state of the speaker stating what to do incase he/she is in the hearer's position i.e., 'leaving him straight away' which is the primary goal. Yet when a language user hears it in an angry emotive force and associate the verbal action or state assumed by the speaker by positioning himself/herself as the hearer to 'be measured as', 'be causing' or 'be deserving' anger, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker's mere suggestion on his 'desire' but rather 'speaker's wish' to 'Warn' on a hearer's 'state' to 'be causing anger' such that there's a need to perform an action of 'leaving him straight away'. Note that, an emotive force has a focus on the first part of the surface structure because of the logical structure of conditions mentioned in an utterance namely, 'the state of being a hearer' and 'what follows after assuming the hearer's position'

The second information of the speaker's assumed 'state' to be causing a specific emotional state is an attempt to get the hearer to do something based on an angry emotive force. It performs a function of 'Warning' to move out of a state causing anger. Utterance 2(d) is thus thought to have undergone functional transfiguration within a directive speech act from 'suggesting' to 'warning'. Another form of functional change in directive speech act is in utterance 2(e) above.

3. Functional transfiguration in Commissive speech acts.

A commissive is an utterance committing the speaker (in varying degrees) to some future course of action. What is common in all commissive utterances is ‘world to word direction of fit’ and ‘Intention sincerity condition’. Searle (1979). They perform functions such as promising, threatening, oath, etc. For example, an utterance ‘I promise to be your best friend’ is a commissive if the speaker has an intention to perform a verbal action of being the hearer’s best friend in the future course of time.

Sentence 3(a) and (b), and 3(c) and (d) show change in functions due to introduction of an emotive force. Note that, an emotive force is related to propositional force by assigning a new force to a propositional force to be ‘as measured as’, ‘as causing’, or ‘as deserving’ an emotive force.

3(a) I do (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Oath, Goal: Intention).

Sentence 3(a) is a commissive by virtue of it having ‘an intention’ of the speaker as a response of committing oneself for the verbal action/state asked by the first speaker. This commitment intention-based goal has been used to perform a function of an oath.

3(b) I do (Emotive force: Sadness, Function: Surrendering, Goal: Intention).

When a language user hears utterance 3(b) being spoken in a sadness emotive force and associate the verbal action or state committed by the speaker to ‘be measured as’, ‘be causing’ or ‘be deserving’ sadness, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker’s mere ‘intention’ for ‘commitment’ but rather ‘intention’ for ‘commitment causing sadness’ which implies intention to perform a function of surrendering.

3(c) I’ll come for you tomorrow (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Promising, Goal: Intention)

Utterance 3(c) is a commissive by virtue of it having ‘an intention’ of the speaker committing oneself for the verbal action of ‘coming for you tomorrow’. This commitment of an intention-based goal has been used to perform a function of a promise.

3(d) I’ll come for you tomorrow (Emotive force: Angry, Function: Threatening, Goal: Intention).

When a language user hears utterance 3(d) being spoken in an angry emotive force and associate the verbal action committed by the speaker to ‘be measured as’, ‘be causing’ or ‘be deserving’ anger, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker’s mere ‘intention’ for ‘commitment’ but rather ‘intention’ for ‘commitment measured as angry toward the hearer’ which implies intention to perform a function of threatening.

Another case with ‘commissive speech acts’ is when a facial expression is used by the hearer to give a response to a directive speech act of the speaker ‘to be deserving’ the verbal action/state expressed in a propositional force, in this case the hearer’s facial expression is indirectly performing a ‘commissive response speech act’ as a response to the speaker’s ‘directive speech act’ performing ‘a questioning function’, a good example is 3(f) as the response to 3(e) below.

3(e) Are you happy working with us?

3 (f) Happiness facial expression (Emotive force: Happiness, Function: Oath, Goal: Intention).

4. Functional transfiguration in Expressive speech acts.

An expressive is an utterance expressing the psychological state specified in the sincerity condition about state of affairs specified in the propositional content. Searle (1979). What is common in all expressive utterances is ‘psychological state’ and according to Searle there is no ‘Direction of fit in an expressive’. Expressive utterances function to thank, congratulate, apologize, condole, deplore, welcome. Etc.

Sentence 4(a) and (b), and 4(c) and (d) show change in functions due to introduction of an emotive force. Note that, an emotive force is related to propositional force by assigning a new force to a propositional force to be ‘as measured as’, ‘as causing’, or ‘as deserving’ an emotive force.

4(a) Thank you. (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Thanking, Goal: Psychological state)

Utterance 4(a) is an expressive speech act by virtue of it having ‘a psychological state’ of the speaker performing a function of ‘Thanking’ the hearer. Note that, neutral emotive force has been used to refer to utterance based emotional expression, a happiness emotional facial expression may as well accompany a thanking expressive.

4(b) Thank you. (Emotive force: Disgust, Function: Deploring indirectly, Goal: Psychological state)

When a language user hears utterance 4(b) being spoken in a disgust emotive force and associate the state stated by the speaker to 'be measured as', 'be causing' or 'be deserving' anger, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker's expression of a 'Thanking' psychological state but rather 'intention' to indirectly state the 'disgust psychological state' to be deserving the verbal action/state it is responding to, which indirectly performs a deploring function.

4(c) I apologize for stepping on your foot. (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Apologizing, Goal: Psychological state)

Utterance 4(c) is an expressive speech act by virtue of it having 'a psychological state' of the speaker performing a function of 'Apologizing' to the hearer.

4(d) I apologize for stepping on your foot. (Emotive force: Happiness, Function: Ridicule, Goal: Desire).

When a language user hear utterance 4(d) being spoken in a happiness emotive force and associate the psychological state stated by the speaker to 'be measured as', 'be causing' or 'be deserving' happiness, it may likely force the hearer to create another reference apart from speaker's expression of 'An apology' but rather 'intention' to indirectly state the 'happiness psychological state' to be deserving the verbal action/state of 'stepping on a foot' of the recipient of an apology and hearer. Utterance 4(d) is thus indirectly performing a 'ridiculing function' of a directive speech act using the surface structure of an expressive speech act which shift focus from 'stating psychological state' which is the unique goal of an expressive speech act to 'desire' to point/highlight on the verbal action which imply a ridicule which is the unique goal of a directive speech act.

5. Functional transfiguration in declarative speech acts.

A declaration is 'an utterance that represents reality as changed in their propositional content so as to change it'. Searle (1979). The unique goal of a declarative speech act is not based on transmitting information to the hearer before an action but involving the hearer in the process of an action of changes. Declarative speech acts perform functions such as granting, giving, judging, deciding, prohibiting,

cancelling, classifying, creating, allowing, appointing, etc., what is common in all declarative utterances is 'a declaration'. According to Searle, there is no 'sincerity condition' in a declarative speech act. For example, 'I now declare you husband and wife'. Since a sincerity condition is lacking in a declarative utterance, a declarative speech act is only responsive to only three felicity conditions (Propositional content condition, Preparatory condition, and Essential condition). This is because a sincerity condition is 'an information meaning' based condition, while a declarative speech act is 'an information action' based act. Introduction of an emotive force to a declarative utterance doesn't seem to cause much influence as it does to some utterances of other speech act categories. This may be an indicator of the information (content) relationship between a sincerity condition and an emotive force. To be sincere in a sincerity condition means 'Meaning what you say in the surface structure of an utterance' and to signify with an emotive force means 'Forcing a hearer to acquire meaning from an interplay of the surface structure and emotional expression'. Reference as a component of meaning appears to be fixed to the goal of a declarative utterance surface structure i.e., involving the hearer in an action of changes rather than transmitting information to the hearer. What sets a declarative speech act apart from other four categories of speech acts is 'an act to change involving the hearer in the utterance surface structure' rather than 'transmitting information to the hearer' in form of Informing (Assertive), Encouraging (Directive), Committing (Commissive), or Expressing (Expressive).

Sentences 5(a), 5(b), and 5(c) show no change in functions due to introduction of an emotive force. This is because the propositional force in the surface structure of a declarative speech act is not based on a sincerity condition which is the condition most prone to influences of an emotive force in the felicity conditions. It may be because the power vested to the performer of a declarative speech act is emotionally agreeing with any emotive force and despite the introduced emotion category, an action determined by the surface structure of a declarative utterance is independently obliged to change.

5(a) I declare this meeting is (hereby) adjourned. (Emotive force: Neutral, Function: Declare, Goal: Declaration).

5(b) I declare this meeting is (hereby) adjourned. (Emotive force: Angry, Function: Declare, Goal: Declaration).

5(c) I declare this meeting is (hereby) adjourned. (Emotive force: Contempt, Function: Declare, Goal: Declaration).

3.3 Emotional Signification Pragmatic Act Mismatches.

Think for instance of a traditional semantic distinction where there is no an established set of rules linking facial expressions, voice, and utterance defining baseline functional specific semantic interplay, or mismatches of the three, as a result, what speakers want to mean with their words, voices and facial expressions gets at risk of pragmatically ‘meaning, performing or intending’ something else and that’s where an interlocution gets vague.

The utterance, ‘If I were you, I’d leave him straight away’ is semantically referent and acceptable, not until it is heard and observed being spoken repeatedly by different people and with different facial expressions. That’s where an indexical argument rises.

Speaking it with a ‘sadness’ facial expression may sound compositionally agreeing with ‘Felicity conditions’ discussed in part 3.2 about Emotional signification as a speech act, with a conclusion that ‘an emotional signification act’ carries an emotive force which influences or violates felicity conditions and other pragmatic forces building a speech act.

Now observing ‘propositional contents’ present in or associated with facial expressions emotive force as compared to that of an utterance surface structure, may still hint on the relationship between two modalities of information in interlocution, which are, ‘the utterance propositional contents’ and ‘emotional contents subdivided into two modalities, i.e., facial expressions and voice’. The functional form that the information modalities (utterance and emotive face/voice) form to perform a function e.g., Negation, Reversion, Deviation, and Referencing, may have essential information explaining the nature of speakers’ intendedness.

For instance, the relationship between ‘utterance propositional contents’ and ‘facial expressions propositional contents’, may form a ‘negation’ functional form, this may be used as a closer comparative functional rule to start with.

Following cross-modal (face-words) ‘negation rule’ to test changes in meaning through an utterance propositional contents and facial expressions propositional contents. First, the face may be divided into two groups, first, the face that opposes an utterance (+ve negation/there is negation), and second the face that agrees with an utterance (-ve negation/there is no negation). Then looking on the semantic nature of an utterance propositional contents the same may be observed in the other way as, first, an utterance that opposes facial expression propositional contents, and second, an utterance that agrees with facial expression propositional contents which draws an assumption that ‘any face that does not agree with an utterance, be it opposite or otherwise, is pragmatically affording emotional signification. i.e., it is an emotional expression pragmatic act’. This is where the main argument on chapter 3.3. Emotional signification as a pragmatic act, rises.

With ‘negation rule’, lets observe an utterance.

1. I’m so happy to meet you. (With happiness facial expression).
2. I’m so happy to meet you. (With sadness facial expression).

Sentences 1 and 2 above are semantically obvious that, they have a proposition that is said by the speaker to the hearer, it has a message with an encoder’s perspective on his state of mind regarding meeting the decoder and when spoken with a ‘happiness’ facial expression it agrees (-ve negation) with the speaker’s ‘utterance propositional contents’ yet when spoken with ‘sadness’ facial expression it opposes (+ve negation) the speaker’s ‘utterance propositional contents’ which rises indexical oddness on the meaning intended by the speaker due to ‘ambiguity in mental state truth conditions’, i.e., whether is happiness mental state existing in the speaker.

The ‘state of mind’ represented by an ‘emotive force’ and ‘utterance propositional contents’ cannot be expressed with double propositions to perform more than one emotional signification act at the same time due to limited mental states truth conditions on existence of two opposite mental states at the same person at the same time, unless an utterance receive influences in its meanings, functions/intentions as it is the

case in functional transfiguration in Searle's taxonomy of speech acts. Thus, indexical oddness on the meaning intended by the speaker in 'negation rule' applied in 'utterance-face propositional contents mismatch' may otherwise bring about another component analysis functional rule that is 'cross-modal reversion', A proposition is self-reversible based on two emotional expressions modes i.e., face and words of an utterance. For instance, when a facial expression makes an utterance proposition opposite of the surface structure proposition as in utterance 3, 4, and 5 below. In these examples, Reversion rule causes a facial expression to reduce the degree of sincerity in the utterance propositional force leading to loss or decrease in the degree of meaning.

3. I'm not pleased with you coming here. (With happiness facial expression)
4. I'm not happy (With happiness facial expression)
5. I hate seeing you (With happiness facial expressions)

Cross modal reversion differs from cross modal negation in a way that in 'reversion' a face makes the whole proposition insincere leading to loss or decrease in degree of meaning. The speaker may be using reversion to lower the degree of intention or hiding a positive proposition to the hearer using a negative utterance while retaining its correct emotive force in a facial expression. While 'negation' makes a face and an utterance appearing to be negating each other as the speaker tries to hide a negative proposition using a positive utterance. In 'negation' the utterance and face are both miss-formed to signify an intention that may be different from both the face and an utterance while in 'reversion' it is only one (the utterance or facial expression) that is miss-formed making the other function as a baseline of a proposition at which reversion is done.

However, in the following examples from 6 to 10 and the 'negation rule' and 'reversion rule' don't seem to fit in, because, neither the face nor the utterance is independently holding a signified function of the mismatches.

6. I'm so happy to meet you. (With angry facial expression).
7. I'm so happy to meet you. (With contempt facial expression).
8. I'm so happy to meet you. (With fear facial expression).
9. I'm so happy to meet you. (With surprise facial expression).

10. I'm so happy to meet you. (With disgust facial expressions).

In case cross-modal functional form of 'negation' and 'reversion' can't be characterized as pragmatic cross modal component analysis functional rule features, because of presence of newer implied meanings in interplaying or mismatching relationship as in 6 to 10 above, there may still be other functional forms formed thereafter, for instance based on seven universal facial expressions where one facial expression may be used as an 'utterance associate' and the remaining six as opposite/reversing (if any) and 'pragmatically affording' new meanings.

Let's regard six of universal facial expressions pragmatically affording new meanings as 'deviators' since they don't agree with an utterance propositional content meaning and five of them may not be opposing as well. In such cases, the interplaying and mismatching relationship between utterance and emotional face/voice, forms a newer functional form as a deviating form, which may be used in deriving the third functional rule as a 'Deviation Rule'.

Up to this stage any interplaying or mismatch that does not form a form of negation, reversion, or deviation of an emotional utterance propositional content, may be assigned to a functional rule as a 'referencing' emotional signification, since it is semantically identified as 'a baseline referent emotional interplay with which language users apply as dominant in articulating a particular emotional utterance'.

This bring the fourth conclusive baseline functional rule that is 'referencing rule' as a rule remaining after the interplaying failure of six mismatching faces while retaining only one referencing face after testing the conflict of an utterance as a linguistic sign and seven Ekman's emotional facial expressions as emotion indexes with three pragmatic affordance functional rules of emotional signification i.e., Negation, Reversion, and Deviation. See table 3.6 below for a compiled summary.

Table 3:6 Emotional signification cross-modal semantic and pragmatic components analysis table of the utterance "I'm so happy to meet you."

Rules/Emotional expressions	Happiness	Sadness	Anger	Contempt	Fear	Surprise	Disgust
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Negation	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
Reversion	-	+	-	-	-	-	-
Deviation	-	+	+	+	+	+	+
Referencing	+	-	-	-	-	- (- & +)	-

Therefore based on the compiled cross-modal semantic and pragmatic components analysis table above, Language users may rely on emotional signification pragmatic affordances to derive the way to speak emotional utterances and come up with indexical arguments to associate such affordances as pragmatic acts of functional specific speeches such as jokes, insults, warnings, suggestions, advice, or other emotional languages speech acts and implications based on their emotional valences and semantic contents of an utterance.

The decision on ‘facial emotional valence’ may be based on the ‘baseline utterance propositional contents’ where there may be a face that negates an utterance proposition, reverses an utterance proposition, deviates from an utterance proposition or refer to an utterance proposition, yet the question remains on decisions about ‘emotional utterance surface structure proposition valence’, and ‘emotional voice/face proposition valence’.

It may be possible if the baseline mode with which emotional valence are compared to is changed from ‘utterance surface structure propositional contents’ to ‘facial propositional contents’ or ‘voice propositional contents’ assuming what controls interlocution signification is the ‘symbolic face’ as a representative of state of mind rather than ‘symbolic words’ or ‘symbolic voice’ where semantic and pragmatic oddness is observed in the facial expressions proposition based on baseline assumptions built in with the face and deciding the valence of a proposition based on the baseline face or voice, which still brings challenges to the property of language as ‘symbolic’.

Observing the property ‘symbolic’, whether the symbolic nature in the system of language means only the ‘words’ ‘rather’ than ‘face’ and or ‘voice’ raises a semiotic challenge to whether a symbol /sign can be a word, a face, and a voice when all the three are used at the same time in an act of speaking and seem not

to symbolize the same proposition. If the language property 'symbolic' and the word 'symbol/sign' in the system of language means mere words, the question is why do faces mean otherwise? Why do voices mean otherwise? Do words, face and voice need to align for the so-called 'oral language' to be symbolic and mean the same thing in the system of language? If not, are faces and voices not symbolic, and why can't facial expressions and voice be observed as symbols (indexes) at the growing semantic and syntactic levels, as it is the case for words as symbols at the surface structure involving low to high levels of meaning namely, morpheme level, word level, phrasal level, clause level, and sentence level, do the face and voices symbolic nature change as they grow into high levels? All these questions may be necessary in guiding the linguist when deciding on the criteria for defining 'emotional utterance proposition valence'.

However, in dealing with utterance propositional contents valence, since spoken utterances as pragmatic acts acquire additional meanings, functions/intentions based on emotional affordances. Affordances, that an utterance acquires makes an utterance such as, "If I were you, I'd leave him straight away" a pragmatic act of at least four categories.

- A. When spoken with negative emotional facial expression it may be interpreted as a warning.
- B. with positive emotional facial expression, it may be interpreted as an advice or wish.
- C. with neutral emotional facial expression, it may be interpreted as a threat and opinion.
- D. on a written paper/written text it may be interpreted as an advice.

Therefore, the conclusion on the functions and intendedness of the pragmatic utterance 'If I were you, I'd leave him straight away' in A to D above, may be built in change in the propositional contents valence of two meaning making aspect of language as symbolic, where the change in facial expression as a unique symbol affects the change in propositional contents of words/utterance as a symbol(s). The four categories above may lead one to think of propositional contents valence as utterance specific because of it also being emotional.

CHAPTER FOUR RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Having reviewed and laid down a theoretical foundation on studying meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and an utterance in both semiotics and pragmatics, the following chapter focuses on the role of the second objective in empirical confirmation of the first objective that is to find evidence supporting presence of pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of a face, voice, and an utterance in interlocution, and investigating the foundation on studying meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and an utterance in English sentences and English speech acts. The focus is on differences an utterance acquires when accompanied with different emotional expressions during the process of English language emotional signification and whether such differences can be presented to English listeners in semi-natural simulated audio dialogues and be perceived to be having different intentions as conditioned.

The first experiment is designed to find out acoustic differences in an English utterance when spoken in eight different emotional expressions in terms of mean amplitudes of an emotional speech signal. The processes used to analyze the mean amplitude are, first, identification of a propositional content in a sentence and a propositional act in a speech act, and then affirming the relationship between utterance proposition to be measured as an emotion category accompanying an utterance, deserving an emotion category accompanying an utterance, or causing an emotion category accompanying an utterance, and second, identifying and detecting matches and mismatches of utterance 'linguistic emotion' with 'prosodic emotion' using mean amplitude of a speech signal in form of simulated emotional signification from utterance linguistic specific emotion category to other eight emotion categories, namely, neutral emotion, Sadness, Anger, Happiness, Fear, Disgust, Contempt, and Surprise.

It is then hypothesized that, since emotions as carriers of utterance meanings may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intention of an utterance unless there are theoretical explanations of how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions, there is therefore an additional utterance intention listener judgement experiment (Experiment two) which uses matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses to dialogues

formulated by consulting explanations laid in the theoretical foundation part that, not all types of sentence and or classes of Searle speech acts react similarly in terms of utterance function and intention when affected by emotional signification.

Thus, the methodology employed in this research includes the combination of quantitative (phonetics experiments) and qualitative (linguistic research survey) which serves confirm empirical foundation of the Theoretical foundation chapter.

The theoretical foundation chapter describes an approach to understanding utterance meanings, functions, and intentions which are present in matches and mismatches of emotional facial expressions, voice emotions and utterance linguistic content during interlocution by focusing on the concept 'emotional signification'. The methodology uses two research methods which are two phonetics experiments which are; Utterance emotion categories detection experiment and speech acts emotional signification phonetic experiment, and one linguistic survey about Utterance intention listener judgement.

4.1 Research Questions.

This research attempts to answer the following two questions.

A. Do English speakers interpret an utterance spoken in different emotional expressions to be having different meanings, intentions, and functions?

B. What are possible pragmatic meanings, intentions, and functions that an English speaker expresses when interplaying and mismatching facial expressions, voice, and utterance meaning?

4.2 Phonetics Experiment 1.

Purpose

An experiment was set out to determine whether different emotion categories of speech presupposed to have deviations in utterance specific meaning, functions, and intentions can be acoustically manifested.

To reach this objective, a semi natural simulated audio English emotional utterances database was created where ten English emotional utterances were spoken in eight (08) emotional significations. Selected emotional expressions were modal emotion/neutral emotion, Sadness, Anger, Happiness, Fear, Disgust, Contempt, and Surprise.

Participants

Ten (10) Participants were recruited, five (05) of them were Chinese native speakers studying at Nanjing normal university representing experiment group one (01), and the other five (05) participants were English speakers other than British and Chinese, who were also studying at Nanjing normal university who represented experiment group two (02). The purpose of categorizing them into two groups was primarily to look for social linguistic variables related or correlated to Emotional signification. None of the participants had a history of acoustic surgery or any voice or face related impairment. The participant's task was to speak out ten English utterances with each of the dominant eight emotional expressions while his/her voice being recorded. Each participant signed a written consent form prior to an experiment and was rewarded a sum of 150 yuan for that support.

Design

The experiment was conducted at the Phonetic science and speech technology laboratory at the School of Psychology at Suiyuan Campus at Nanjing normal university. Experiment groups were categorized into three groups as follows.

1. Control group

A synthesis of Text to speech engine (TTS) from the website <http://texttospeechrobot.com> was used to voice out each of the ten experiment's utterances as the neutral/modal speech in 09/29/2022. The language category selected was v4 British English (en-GB): kate V3[IBM-Female, enhanced dnn] where each of the synthesized utterances were saved in a personal computer as mp3 files. Then mp3 files synthesized at 22500Hz were converted into 44100Hz wav files encoded with mono 32-bit float format using Audacity

software. In this category, the essence of the term ‘control group’ were simply a label assuming the ‘baseline measurement’ which can be used to test whether same species of different characteristics can show observable variations as compared to the ‘baseline measurement’.

2. Experiment group one (01)

This group comprised five Chinese native participants each one was required to speak out ten English utterances with each of the dominant eight emotional expressions while his/her voice being recorded.

3. Experiment group two (02)

This group comprised five participants other than British and Chinese natives, each one was required to speak out ten English utterances with each of the dominant eight emotional expressions while his/her voice being recorded.

Stimuli preparation and Pilot.

The following ten English utterances were created to be spoken by the three experiment groups.

1. I'm so happy to meet you! How are you doing?
2. Guess what we found in the garden! A pair of gloves, guns, and that stolen gold!
3. I'd like to have chocolates, mirinda and some banana again.
4. Why are you sitting here? It's cold outside! Get inside!
5. Of course, you are right, especially reading inspiring quotes
6. Who wouldn't have gone to school to fulfill their dreams?
7. Could you find out what's a point of surprising us with another plastic surgery?
8. I mean they were doing it correctly from the very beginning.
9. They were aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs like that.
10. In nine hours of a goodnight, he didn't hear the first disgusting top hazard to mankind.

Logical Affirmation of Linguistic propositions with prosodic emotion in Sentences preparation and pilot.

A proposition is the main thought (sense) of an utterance. Sense of a speech act is a propositional act, and sense of an utterance other than a speech is its propositional content. According to Hansen and Hessman (2007), Propositional content, or 'sentence meaning,' is largely determined by functional units that have traditionally been called topics and predications (or 'comments'): the topic is what a sentence is about, whereas the predication specifies what is being said about the topic. Also, Moltmann (2003) on the traditional view of meaning, regards the meaning of a sentence to be possibly determined by contextual factors and that meaning is taken to be a proposition or propositional content. Moltmann (2003) proposes that, a proposition, as traditionally conceived, is an entity that has truth conditions essentially, can be shared by different intentional agents, and can act as the content of different kinds of propositional attitudes (e.g., belief, hope, knowledge) as well as different kinds of speech acts (e.g., assertion, request, question). Propositional contents thus play a role both for an agent's mental state and for his various contributions in a conversation context. Intentionality means mental representation of existence. According to a French philosopher Jean-Paul Sartre (2012) on 'Being and Nothingness', "Intentionality is consciousness". And consciousness is existence in mind and existence in reality/in the world. In other words, 'Utterance intentionality' means existence of an utterance proposition in the human mind e.g., existence of happiness mental state in mind in the utterance 'I am happy to see you', or in reality/in the world e.g., existence of Venus in the sky in the utterance 'That is the morning star'.

The difference in utterance proposition form between speech acts and the four types of English sentence is that, In Searle speech acts categories. The proposition form of each of the categories of Searle speech acts is an illocutionary point. i.e., The basic purpose of a speaker in making an utterance. A component of illocutionary force at which the purpose of a speech act is built. And in four types of sentences, the proposition form is, according to Aristotelian logic, a particular kind of sentence (e.g., a declarative sentence) that affirms or denies a predicate of a subject, optionally with the help of a copula. A copula (copular verb, linking verb) is a word or phrase that links/ties the subject of a sentence to subject complement. E.g., the word 'Is' in He is a teacher. In English language copular verbs are verbs to be. Propositions stand as carriers of utterance intention and can be affected differently when introduced to

influence of intentional intonation and intentional emotional signification. The reason being that a spoken utterance is a multi-modal presentation of communicative contents and propositions in three modes, namely, linguistic words, prosodic contents such as intonation pattern, and emotions which can be represented by an emotional voice or facial expressions.

Utterance number seven; ‘Could you find out what’s a point of surprising us with another plastic surgery?’ is an Interrogative sentence and utterance number nine; ‘They were aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs like that.’ is a declarative sentence. The nature of matches and mismatches investigated and detected bases on propositional contents as a criterion for identification of linguistic emotion of an utterance and mental state represented prosody and facial expressions. Detecting matches and mismatches of utterance linguistic emotion with prosodic emotion using mean amplitude manifestation of utterance seven (7) requires use of the same logical affirmation of propositional content intentionality in a multi-modal utterance, namely, the propositional content, is measured as its accompanying emotion category, deserving its accompanying emotion category, or causing its accompanied emotion category, it is convincing to associate the propositional content of Sentence number seven, that is; ‘Finding out a reason for the surprise’, as composed of neutral linguistic emotion since ‘the questioning for information about a reason for the previous surprise’ that is explicitly stated in the propositional content of utterance number seven which is an interrogative sentence should be measured as emotionally neutral, deserving neutral emotion, and causing neutral emotion to the hearer. The matches of linguistic emotion of an utterance with prosodic emotion of an utterance in utterance number seven is thus speaking it with a prosodic neutral emotion. The mismatches of linguistic emotion of an utterance with prosodic emotion of an utterance in utterance number seven is speaking it with a prosodic emotion other than the neutral emotion which is manifested by its linguistic propositional content. In this case the manifestation of mismatches in utterance number seven is on mean amplitude of the other seven emotion categories used in speaking it by each of the ten speakers.

Also, detecting matches and mismatches of utterance linguistic emotion with prosodic emits accompanied amplitude manifestation of utterance nine (9) requires use of the same logical affirmation of propositional content intentionality in a multi-modal utterance, namely, the propositional content, is measured as its

accompanying emotion category, deserving its accompanying emotion category, or causing its accompanied emotion category. It is convincing to associate the propositional content of Sentence number nine that is; 'They were aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs like that.' as composed of sadness linguistic emotion since the assertion of the three categories of information namely -being aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs by the subject -they is explicitly stating a proposition of realizing a sadness state in a declarative sentence which can be measured as emotionally sad, deserving sadness emotion, and causing sadness emotion to the hearer. The matches of linguistic emotion of an utterance with prosodic emotion of an utterance in utterance number nine is thus speaking it with a prosodic sadness emotion. The mismatches of linguistic emotion of an utterance with prosodic emotion of an utterance in utterance number nine is speaking it with a prosodic emotion other than the sadness emotion which is manifested by its linguistic propositional content. In this case the manifestation of mismatches in utterance number seven is on mean amplitude of the other seven emotion categories used in speaking it by each of the ten speakers. The acoustic detectability of matches and mismatches of utterance 'linguistic emotion' with 'prosodic emotion' using mean amplitude as indicated in analysis of utterance seven (7) and nine (9), provide a foundational explanation to presence of distinctive physiological features of speeches happening due to speaker's emotional signification of the spoken utterances.

Data Collection

Audio files of experimental group one was collected by recording speakers' voices of the above ten English utterances by a microphone connected to a laboratory computer with adobe audition software version 12 (cc 2019) and downloaded as wav files.

Voice files with noises were denoised with Spectral subtraction noise reduction method in a Teclast personal computer with Praat analysis software version 6.2 at 0.025 window lengths, a filter frequency ranging from 80.0 to 10000.0 Hz, a smoothing bandwidth of 40.0 Hz and a noise reduction of negative -20dB.

Audio files of control group were collected through a synthesis of Text to speech engine (TTS) from the website <http://texttospeechrobot.com> which was used to voice out each of the ten experiment's utterances

as the neutral/modal speech in 09/29/2022. The language category selected was v4 British English (en-GB): kate V3[IBM-Female, enhanced dnn] where each of the synthesized utterances were saved in a personal computer as mp3 files. Then mp3 files synthesized at 22500Hz were converted into 44100Hz wav files encoded with mono 32-bit float format using Audacity software.

4.3 Phonetics Experiment 2.

Purpose

An experiment was set out to determine whether different emotion categories of speech presupposed to have utterance specific functions and intentions can be acoustically perceived as having different intentions by English listeners.

To reach this objective, a semi natural simulated audio English language database was created where a total of Seventeen (17) English dialogues was spoken by two speakers. A male speaker was the researcher, and a female speaker was the experiment participant.

Participants

One (1) Participant was recruited as one of dialogue speakers, another speaker was the researcher. Forty-two (42) other participants participated by responding to research survey where they were required to listen to Seventeen (17) short dialogues between two speakers on each question and select intention of the second speaker from the four options after each question. Respondents were also required to select their profession category and age group in question number 18 and 19.

Design

The experiment design was conducted at the Phonetic science and speech technology laboratory at School of Psychology at Suiyuan campus of Nanjing normal university.

Stimuli preparation and pilot.

The following Seventeen (17) sets of dialogues were spoken, recorded, and distributed in a research survey where English listeners were supposed to select an intention of the second speaker (speaker B) from four options after each dialogue.

1(a) Do you accept working here?

1(b) I do. (Neutral emotion category)

2(a) Do you accept working here?

2(b) I do. (Sadness emotion category)

3(a) Do you accept working here?

3(b) I do. (Angry emotion category)

4(a) John is coming again to see me.

4(b) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Neutral emotion category)

5(a) Rose is coming again to see me.

5(b) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Angry emotion category)

6(a) Rose is coming again to see me.

6(b) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (Sadness emotion category)

7(a) Sophia will come to your shop today.

7(b) She likes candies. (Neutral emotion category)

8(a) Sophia will come to your shop today.

8(b) She likes candies. (Surprised emotion category)

9(a) My kid will come to your shop today.

9(b) She likes candies. (Disgust emotion category)

10(a) I'll be cooking with you today.

10(b) Can you pass the salt. (Neutral emotion category)

11(a) I'll be cooking with you today.

11(b) Can you pass the salt. (Contempt emotion category)

12(a) See you.

12(b) I'll come for you tomorrow. (Neutral emotion category)

13(a) See you.

13(b) I'll come for you tomorrow. (Angry emotion category)

14(b) That is my gift (Surprised emotion category)

15(b) I apologize for stepping on your foot (Neutral emotion category)

16(b) I apologize for stepping on your foot (Sadness emotion category)

17(b) I apologize for stepping on your foot (Happiness emotion category)

CHAPTER FIVE RESEARCH ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

5.1. Analysis and Results of Experiment One.

Speeches used in daily conversations are rich in intended and unintended functions and emotional intents manifested in different acoustic components perceivable and unperceivable by the human ear. Complexity of emotional categories and diversity of individual human speech sounds make it only easier to perceive functions and emotional intentions from emotional utterances which are often encountered or are mostly used in a particular language community than the less encountered. Though, both familiar and unfamiliar functions of signified emotional utterances tend to manifest speech differences such as amplitude. Mean amplitude has been found to be the most distinctive acoustic feature in this experiment.

Mean Amplitude

Amplitude is the sound pressure level. Sound pressure is the force of sound on the surface area perpendicular to the direction of the sound. Its SI unit is Pascal. An audio signal amplitude is equivalent to the loudness of an audio signal. It is the amount of maximum displacement of vibrating particles of the medium from the mean position when the sound is being produced. The amplitude of an audio signal measures the height of the audio wave, that is the distance between the crest/trough and the mean position of the wave. Amplitude is measured in decibels (dB) which is the sound pressure level.

The relationship between sound pressure level (Amplitude) and emotion categories is in 'excitation occurring at the glottal air track'. Emotional arousal that accompanies an utterance contributes to how subglottal pressure is tuned and released affecting minimum and maximum amplitudes of the structure of a spoken utterance. The change in emotion categories used in speaking an utterance to perform different functions and intentions affect the change in the structure of subglottal air pressure that is released when the person is speaking with arousal. Two utterances, utterance 7 and utterance 9 are picked out for analysis of mean amplitudes. There was no found reliable empirical data on differences in patterns correlating the influence of variable 'Participants sociolinguistic groups' in emotional signification as primarily

categorized in three participants groups, namely, control group, experimental group one, and experimental group two. The differences found to be showing distinct meaningful empirical data are in ‘overall participants fluctuation in mean amplitude’ and ‘Overall emotion categories fluctuation in mean amplitude’ which are independent of sociolinguistic group differences as formatted and distinguished in experiment group one and experiment group two.

In the analysis of Mean amplitude fluctuation in decibels and valence in eight emotion categories of two sentences, the first sentence, i.e., sentence 7, has been repeated as figure 5.1 and figure 5.2 to indicate difference in analysis of decibels fluctuation in number of participants and decibels fluctuation in valence. The same repetition in figures has been done to the second sentence, i.e., sentence 9 as figure 5.3 and figure 5.4 to indicate differences in analysis of decibels fluctuation in number of participants and decibels fluctuation in valence of emotions.

Utterance 7.

The sentence used is, “Could you find out what’s a point of surprising us with another plastic surgery?”, with its phonetic description as; /kəd jʊ faɪnd aʊt wɒts ə pɔɪnt əv səˈpraɪzɪŋ əs wɪð əˈnʌðəˈplæstɪk ˈsɜːdʒəri?/. It was recorded with a sampling rate of 44.1 KHz. An overall mean amplitude distribution by 10 participants (P) in 8 different emotional signification (S) of utterance 7 is shown in table 5.1 below.

Utterance 7 Mean amplitudes distribution table.

Table 5:1 An overall mean amplitude distribution in decibels (dB) by 10 participants in 8 different emotional signification of utterance 7.

Emotional Signification	P1s7	P2s7	P3s7	P4s7	P5s7	P6s7	P7s7	P8s7	P9s7	P10s7
Angry	-1.039	6.301	-2.405	6.924	-1.478	-4.358	-4.314	2.502	-5.231	1.026
Contempt	-1.321	1.970	-4.720	-4.517	3.209	3.592	-4.619	-4.212	-8.014	4.583
Disgust	3.847	-2.802	-2.228	-2.185	-4.917	1.045	-8.861	-2.094	2.604	- 5.352

Fear	3.034	-4.250	4.943	2.743	1.499	-1.902	3.816	-6.752	-1.906	- 8.087
Happiness	1.053	-1.898	1.492	2.872	-1.446	2.747	2.867	2.850	1.038	4.079
Neutral	-1.424	-1.605	-1.234	4.170	5.256	2.456	-6.048	-2.290	-4.088	6.500
Sadness	3.332	2.933	3.074	-5.285	-5.032	2.021	-1.343	-6.761	4.709	4.152
Surprised	-5.491	-1.698	1.479	6.354	-1.945	3.472	5.176	-4.578	-3.404	3.498
Control 7	7.036									

The mean amplitude correlation between variables ‘speaker/participant, emotion and utterance’ is statistically reliable in explaining the differences speakers have in signifying different types of emotions of the same utterances.

The findings as shown in table 5.2 show the mean amplitude ranges plotted from positive +10dB (High) to negative -10dB (Low) and grouped into four, ‘5dB to 10dB’, ‘0dB to 5dB’, ‘-5dB to 0dB’, and ‘-10dB to -5dB’.

Control utterance 7 has high expression in amplitude (dB) ranging from ‘5dB to 10dB’

Angry emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 5/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Contempt emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 5/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’

Disgust emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 5/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’

Fear emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 5/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’

Happiness emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 8/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’

Neutral emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 5/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’

Sadness emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 6/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’

Surprised emotional signification of utterance number 7 has 4/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’

Table 5.2 below shows the mean amplitude ranges of utterance number 7 plotted from positive +10dB (High) to negative -10dB (Low) and grouped into four, '5dB to 10dB', '0dB to 5dB', '-5dB to 0dB', and '-10dB to -5dB.'

Utterance 7 Participants Mean amplitude ranges.

Table 5:2 The mean amplitude ranges of utterance 7 plotted from positive +10dB (High) to negative -10dB (Low) and grouped into four, '5dB to 10dB', '0dB to 5dB', '-5dB to 0dB', and '-10dB to -5dB.'

Range s/No. of Par- ticip- ants in Emo- tion cate- gory	An- gry	Contempt	Dis- gust	Fea- r	Happi- ness	Neu- tral	Sadness	Sur- prise	Con- trol
5-10	2	0	0	0	0	2	0	2	1
0-5	2	4	3	5	8	2	6	3	0
-5-0	5	5	5	2	2	5	1	4	0
-1---5	1	1	1	2	0	1	3	1	0

Another remarkable finding is that participants mean amplitude fluctuate in decibels valence as they change from one emotional signification to another in all the 8 emotional categories and is almost the same in terms of 'rises' from negative to positives (-10 to +10) and 'falls' from positive to negative (+10 to -10).

The finding as shown in figure 5.1-line graph shows utterance 7 fluctuation in dB from one emotional signification to another by each participant.

From Angry to Contempt, emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Contempt to Disgust, emotional signification falls by 5/10 participants and rises by 5/10 participants.

From Disgust to Fear, emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Fear to Happiness, emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Happiness to Neutral, emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Neutral to Sadness, emotional signification falls by 5/10 participants and rises by 5/10 participants.

From Sadness to Surprised, emotional signification falls by 5/10 participants and rises by 5/10 participants.

Utterance 7 Mean amplitude line graph

Figure 5:1A line graph showing utterance 7 mean amplitude fluctuation in dB in 8 emotional categories (Angry, Contempt, Disgust, Fear, Happiness, Neutral, Sadness, Surprised) by 10 participants.

Also, Participants similar emotional signification of the same utterance has been found to be varying differently in terms of mean amplitude valence. i.e., the same emotion category of one utterance by different speakers were expressed in different degrees of amplitudes in both negative decibels and positive decibels as shown in figure 5.2.

The mean amplitude of 'Angry emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 4/10 participants and negative for 6/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Contempt emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 4/10 participants and negative for 6/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Disgust emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 3/10 participants and negative for 7/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Fear emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 5/10 participants and negative for 5/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Happiness emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 8/10 participants and negative for 2/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Neutral emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 4/10 participants and negative for 6/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Sadness emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 6/10 participants and negative for 4/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of 'Surprise emotional signification' of utterance number 7 is positive for 5/10 participants and negative for 5/10 participants.

Utterance 7 Mean amplitude line graph

Figure 5:2A line graph showing utterance 7 Participants Emotional signification mean amplitude fluctuation in valence.

Utterance 9.

The sentence used is “They were aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs like that”, with its phonetic description as; / ðei wər ə'weər əv ðə 'bɔ:riŋ, 'hɜ:tɪŋ, ənd 'mi:niŋlɪs 'prəʊgræmz laɪk ðæt/. It was recorded with a sampling rate of 44.1 KHz. An overall mean amplitude distribution by 10 participants (P) in 8 different emotional signification (S) of utterance 9 is shown in table 4.3 below.

Utterance 9 Mean amplitudes distribution table.

Table 5:3An overall mean amplitude distribution in decibels (dB) by 10 participants in 8 different emotional signification of utterance 9.

Particip ants F/M	Angr y	Contem pt	Disgus t	Fear	Happines s	Neutra l	Sadness	Surprised	Contro l 9
P1s9	6.356	-1.190	1.793	-8.277	-2.307	-3.601	-5.093	-2.075	-2.485
P2s9	-7.305	-8.529	3.378	6.219	1.542	5.154	1.305	-4.249	-2.485
P3s9	-2.671	-2.965	5.635	-1.489	3.337	2.746	4.747	3.303	-2.485
P4s9	-1.056	6.627	-7.325	1.513	-1.897	1.121	2.480	-7.861	-2.485
P5s9	-4.353	7.453	1.307	3.681	3.324	4.677	1.696	1.822	-2.485

P6s9	-2.553	8.471	-3.032	-8.969	-3.236	-1.387	-8.018	-2.345	-2.485
P7s9	-4.596	1.049	3.972	-6.696	5.556	-1.556	3.439	4.263	-2.485
P8s9	-1.861	-3.094	-8.205	-3.610	-1.974	-2.477	9.826	-1.402	-2.485
P9s9	2.016	1.253	3.347	-2.203	5.307	9.546	3.965	-7.442	-2.485
P10s9	9.737	-3.862	1.023	-1.733	-2.236	3.635	-1.436	7.725	-2.485

The mean amplitude correlation between variables ‘speaker/participant, emotion and utterance’ is statistically reliable in explaining the differences speakers have in signifying different types of emotions in the same utterances.

The findings as shown in table 5.4 show the mean amplitude ranges plotted from positive +10dB (High) to negative -10dB (Low) and grouped into four, ‘5dB to 10dB’, ‘0dB to 5dB’, ‘-5dB to 0dB’, and ‘-10dB to -5dB’.

Control utterance number 9 has low expression in amplitude (dB) ranging from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Angry emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 6/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Contempt emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 4/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Disgust emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 6/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’.

Fear emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 4/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Happiness emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 5/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Neutral emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 4/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’ and 4/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’.

Sadness emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 6/10 participants from ‘0dB to 5dB’.

Surprised emotional signification of utterance number 9 has 4/10 participants from ‘-5dB to 0dB’.

Utterance 9 Participants Mean amplitude ranges.

Table 5:4 The mean amplitude ranges of utterance 9 plotted from positive +10dB (High) to negative -10dB (Low) and grouped into four, '5dB to 10dB', '0dB to 5dB', '-5dB to 0dB', and '-10dB to -5dB.'

Range s/No. of Par- ticip- ants in Emo- tion cate- gory	An- gry	Contempt	Dis- gust	Fea r	Happi- ness	Neu- tral	Sadness	Sur- prise	Con- trol
5-10	2	3	1	1	2	2	1	1	0
0-5	1	2	6	2	3	4	6	3	0
-5-0	6	4	1	4	5	4	1	4	1
-1---5	1	1	2	3	0	0	2	2	0

The remarkable finding that 'participants mean amplitude fluctuate in decibels valence as they change from one emotional signification to another in all the 8 emotional categories' is almost the same in terms of 'rises' from negative to positives (-10 to +10) and 'falls' from positive to negative (+10 to -10).

The finding in figure 5.3-line graph shows utterance 9 mean amplitudes fluctuation in dB from 1 emotional signification to another by each participant.

From Angry to Contempt emotional signification falls by 5/10 participants and rises by 5/10 participants.

From Contempt to Disgust emotional signification falls by 4/10 participants and rises by 6/10 participants.

From Disgust to Fear emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Fear to Happiness emotional signification falls by 4/10 participants and rises by 6/10 participants.

From Happiness to Neutral emotional signification falls by 4/10 participants and rises by 6/10 participants.

From Neutral to Sadness emotional signification falls by 6/10 participants and rises by 4/10 participants.

From Sadness to Surprised emotional signification falls by 5/10 participants and rises by 5/10 participants.

Utterance 9 Mean amplitude line graph.

Figure 5:3A line graph showing utterance 9 mean amplitude fluctuation in dB in 8 emotional categories (Angry, Contempt, Disgust, Fear, Happiness, Neutral, Sadness, Surprised) by 10 participants.

Also, Participants similar emotional signification of the same utterance has been found to be varying differently in terms of mean amplitude valence. i.e., the same emotion category of one utterance by different speakers was expressed in different degrees of amplitudes in both negative and positive decibels as shown in figure 5.4 below.

The mean amplitude of ‘Angry emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 3/10 participants and negative for 7/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Contempt emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 5/10 participants and negative for 5/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Disgust emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 7/10 participants and negative for 3/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Fear emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 3/10 participants and negative for 7/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Happiness emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 5/10 participants and negative for 5/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Neutral emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 6/10 participants and negative for 4/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Sadness emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 7/10 participants and negative for 3/10 participants.

The mean amplitude of ‘Surprise emotional signification’ of utterance number 9 is positive for 4/10 participants and negative for 6/10 participants.

Utterance 9 Mean amplitudes.

Figure 5:4A line graph showing utterance 9 Participants Emotional signification mean amplitude fluctuation in valence.

5.2. Analysis and Results of Experiment two.

The relationship between the human voice, emotion categories, and utterance meaning is that an emotional arousal of a specific category tunes the human voice to a specific structure based on utterance constituents. This tuning makes an utterance pragmatically distinctive by the human ear and may be used for different intentions based on the propositional force of an utterance. The finding obtained from the research survey shows that there is no specific intention carried in an emotion category on its own, but rather the same emotion category such as ‘Sadness emotion’ may be used as an emotive force (when an emotion is used to articulate an utterance) to perform different or even contradicting functions/intentions based on the nature of an utterance.

For instance, sadness emotional expression has been empirically shown to perform ‘a surrendering function’ in dialogue 2b, ‘a warning function’ in utterance 6b, and ‘an apologizing function’ in utterance 16b.

Functions which have been empirically found to be performed in dialogues utterances are the most selected choices from the four options in each dialogue as shown in figure 5.5 pie chart below. The next Figure 5.6 show survey participants profession categories distribution pie charts, and age groups frequency distribution pie charts.

Dialogue 3, 7, and 15 are removed from results because they were reported by two survey respondents who encountered errors in audio playing in their devices. Dialogue 8, 11, and 13 are not presented because some of their choices were not selected by two survey respondents.

Figure 5:5 Survey frequency distribution pie charts of dialogues 1,2,4,6,9,10,12,14,16 and 17.

Figure 5:6 Survey participants profession categories and age groups frequency distribution pie charts.

5.3 Results: Words, Voices, and Faces.

Speakers express and interpret spoken utterances in English language by observing a predetermined neutral emotive force which adhere to propositional contents of an utterance and when an emotive force accompanying an utterance is expressed otherwise, they interpret an utterance as having specific conditioned meanings, functions, or intentions. Analyzed data from a linguistic research survey in phonetics experiment two which intended to find out the relationships between the human voice, emotion categories, and utterance meaning, show that hearers engage in meaning making processes to condition and recognize conditioned intentions from utterances which accounts for decisions for responses they give back in interlocution. Such interpretation processing varies from person to person, and it is caused by an emotive force affecting utterance propositional content which is acoustically distinctive by different excitation source features such as Amplitude as analyzed in experiment one.

Pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions presented in a signified emotional utterance have empirically been found to be performing speech acts functions, facial acts, distracting, and performing pragmatic functions such as negation, reversion, deviation, and referencing. Interdependence between ‘empirical enquiries of the theoretical foundation chapter’ and ‘phonetics experiments results in the methodology chapter’, show that the surface structure of a survey sentence ‘I do’ which when spoken as a response to an utterance ‘Do you accept working here?’ is empirically thought to be having a propositional force performing a swearing function in functional transfiguration of commissive speech acts shown in chapter 3.2.4 on Searle taxonomy of speech acts. Due to sadness emotional signification in survey dialogue 2b, an utterance ‘I do’ has been interpreted as having an intention to surrender by 14/42 participants which according to previous empirical enquiries in chapter 3.3 is a reversing type of pragmatic function. (Refer to table 3.6 in chapter 3.3 about emotional signification as a pragmatic act). The same utterance ‘I do’ has also been interpreted as having other intentions such as an intention to complain by 11/42 participants which is a deviating type of pragmatic function, an intention to swear by 9/42 participants which is a referencing type of pragmatic function and an intention to give up by 8/42 participants which is a deviating type of pragmatic function. The differences in survey participants’ interpretation of sadness emotive force used in emotionally signifying a response may be due to individual difference, and differences due to categories of profession or age factors.

Also, the surface structure of a sentence 'I apologize for stepping on your foot' spoken after a verbal action of stepping on someone's foot has been empirically found to be having a propositional force having an apologizing function in functional transfiguration of expressive speech acts in chapter 3.2.4 on functional transfiguration in Searle taxonomy of speech acts. But due to happiness emotional signification the same utterance has been interpreted by survey participants in survey dialogue 17b as having an intention to ridicule by 29/42 participants which is according to previous empirical enquiries a negating type of pragmatic function (Refer to table 3.6 in chapter 3.3 about emotional signification as a pragmatic act) because an apologizing propositional force function of its surface structure is negated by a ridiculing emotional signification force function. The same utterance 'I apologize for stepping on your foot' has also been interpreted as having different intentions such as, an intention to apologize by 6/42 participants which is a reversing type of pragmatic function, an intention to inform by 5/42 participants which is a reversing type of pragmatic function, and an intention to remind by 2/42 participants which is a deviation type of pragmatic function.

On the other hand, the differences in mean amplitude manifestation in multiple utterances of the same emotional signification show how an emotive force and semantic nature of an utterance surface structure affect voice features variation. See figure 5.1, 5.2, 5.3, and 5.4 on how mean amplitudes of angry signification of the voice inputs differs from the first utterance to the tenth utterance, the same is for control synthesized speech utterances 1 to 10. This confirms that any utterance with multiple meanings distinctive by emotional voices used in uttering them can be acoustically comprehended by English listeners as having different intentions.

CHAPTER SIX DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

6.1. Discussion.

This research has been motivated by matches and mismatches between linguistic contents of an utterance, facial expressions, and voice emotions which appear to lead to different meanings, intentions, and functions in interlocution. The motivating reason for setting objectives of this research is the complexity and absence of one to one relationship between emotion categories and intonation categories, and inability of intonation analysis tools to detect multi-modal utterance intention (an intentional matched and mismatched emotional utterance) rather than intonational utterance intentions, since emotions are not sounds and sounds are not emotions even though they can both be used to conditions different utterance meanings and intentions, and can both still be detected differently in acoustic analysis tools. There are therefore two set objectives which are first, laying down foundations to studying pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatching of a face, voice, and an utterance., and second, finding evidence supporting presence of pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of a face, voice, and an utterance in interlocution.

The research review starts by coining a new terminology that is ‘Emotional signification’ that is defined as the property of language where a language user conditions and recognize conditioned pragmatic emotional meanings, functions and intentions through an interplay and mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and an utterance, and which regards an utterance/sentence as a semiotic sign. The research then gives a detailed literature review of the coined terminology as a socio-linguistic problem and as a communication tactic. The review investigates research works on comprehension of utterance’s differences in meaning when spoken and accompanied with facial expressions of different types as a specific form of language competence (emotional signification competence). The literature review highlights such competence from other language related competence to be required in solving socio-linguistic problems of English language. Semiotics and culture have also been precluded as sources of interplay and or mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and utterance as contributing to meanings, functions, and intentions and one noted function of emotional signification has been found to be ‘showing

politeness'. Other meaning making processes through emotional signification have been shown to be resulting from introduction of an emotive force which competes with utterance's surface structure propositional force. Unawareness of EFL learners learning language specific cultural values has also been related to the presumed source of emotional signification challenge. The literature review is also showing research works attempting to identify and detect acoustic manifestation of physiological features of emotion in speech whereby the reviewed research works regard a speech signal as composite of emotion information at different parts of an utterance and in the entire sentence (as a whole) and are mostly investigating matched and mismatched emotional speech signal identification and detection including, Excitation source features, emotion category of a speech, and speaker's attitude. The literature review then shows that what is yet to be researched is empirical enquiries on the scope of emotional signification on how speakers express and interpret emotionally signified utterances, and what pragmatic meanings, functions and intentions are presented when an utterance is spoken in different emotion categories. For this reason, the theoretical foundation covers an approach to understanding meanings, functions and intentions which are presented when an utterance is spoken in different emotion categories, and the research methodology investigates empirical enquiries on the scope of emotional significations on how speakers express and interpret emotionally signified utterances.

Although there is evidence from prosody studies about acoustic detectability of prosodic physiological features manifesting when the same utterance is spoken to indicate different attitude and intentions such as excitation, energy, duration, and loudness, there are still inadequate approaches to how emotional facial expressions, prosodic emotions, and linguistic content of an utterance cause emotional signification, especially given the inability of intonation analysis tools to detect multi-modal utterance intention rather than intonational intentions since emotions are not sounds and sounds are not emotions even though they can both be used to conditions different utterance meanings and intentions, and can both still be detected differently in acoustic analysis tools.

Thus, to investigate the essence of changes in meanings, functions, and intentions due to emotional signification, two phonetics experiments have been applied. The first experiment was designed to find out acoustic differences in an English utterance when spoken in eight different emotional expressions and found mean amplitudes differences. With the aid of Praat speech analysis software, the ready constructed

ten English utterances which were spoken by ten different speakers each in eight different emotional expressions were recorded for experiment analysis. It was then hypothesized that, since emotions as carriers of utterance meanings may not indicate measurable and acoustic detectable intention of an utterance unless there are theoretical explanations of how emotions of both facial expressions and prosody cause different types of utterances to have different meanings, functions, and intentions, there was therefore an additional utterance intention listener judgement experiment which used matched and mismatched emotional speech acts as responses to dialogues formulated by consulting explanations laid in the theoretical foundation part that not all types of sentence and or classes of Searle speech acts react similarly in terms of utterance function and intention when affected by emotional signification. The results of the first experiment confirm that one utterance when spoken with different emotion categories, such emotional manifestations are acoustically detectable. The second phonetic experiment was designed to determine whether different emotional categories of one speech/utterance presupposed to have specific functions and intentions could be physically comprehended by English listeners. In this experiment English listeners responded to multiple choice survey questions attached with English dialogues by selecting the speaker's intention from four options from each dialogue. The results of the second experiment indicate that one speech act utterance when spoken with different emotional voices, its emotional manifestation is interpreted by English listeners as capable of carrying different intentions.

However, there is no one to one relationship between emotion category and utterance intention in a signified emotional utterance. The differences happen because of the baseline emotional nature of an utterance, the nature of an utterance propositional content, and emotional category of a newer emotive force used in signifying an utterance.

There may also be a challenge on whether interpretation of signified emotional meanings using speech experiments is convincing or doubtful. The question on whether interpretation of signified emotional meanings using speech experiments is convincing or doubtful relies on two factors. First is detectability of matches and mismatches of utterance linguistic emotion with prosodic emotion using acoustic features, whereby, in this research mean amplitude has been noted as a distinctive acoustic feature to show that different emotional manifestation of the same speech leads to different acoustic manifestations, namely, amplitude manifestation., and second is detectability of emotional manifestation of speech in acoustics

analysis tools. Therefore, interpretation of specific speech emotional meanings using empirical speech experiments is convincing and reliable only if the researcher explains distinctive physiological and acoustic carriers of speech meanings which can modify speech pragmatic meanings when used differently in the same sentence and are detectable in acoustics analysis tools. However, such detectability may only indicate presence and absence of physiological and acoustic features in a spoken utterance, but not specific meanings present in an utterance. That's where the English listener utterance meaning judgment task comes in. To detect meanings of emotionally modified speeches, there should be listeners speech meaning judgement activity whereby speeches which contain certain emotion specific detectable physiological features are judged by listeners to confirm their intentionality and meanings.

According to Pfitzinger and Kaernbach (2008), Amplitude, as simple as it is, should therefore not be neglected or normalized in acoustic recordings and analyses of emotional speech. In order to estimate a single value representing the amplitude of an utterance Pfitzinger and Kaernbach (2008) compared three different methods; root mean square amplitude, mean absolute amplitude, and amplitude envelope extracted framewise from each utterance in steps of 10ms. Since frames coming from the short speech pauses of 50 ms at the beginning and end of each utterance, or from plosive closures, have very low amplitude values and would distort the mean amplitude of all frames, only 20% of the loudest frames were subjected to averaging, representing the mean of the loudest 20% of each utterance. Their results show that different speakers use amplitude in a different way to express emotions. The mean amplitude values of all neutral utterances differ by only ± 2 dB across speakers. However, in emotional speech the speaker differences range from ± 5 to ± 7 dB.

In this research, different speakers also use amplitude in a different way to express emotions. The mean amplitude values of all neutral utterances differ by ± 1 to ± 10 based on the nature of utterance propositional contents and speakers. In emotional speech the speaker differences range from ± 1 to ± 10 dB. The difference between amplitude measurement in this research and that of Pfitzinger and Kaernbach (2008) is on estimation of a single value representing the amplitude of an utterance, and the number of emotion categories used, whereby, this research examined mean amplitude variation of emotion speeches as caused by different intended emotions of ten actors, namely the Ekman eight categories of speech emotions using Praat speech analysis software while Pfitzinger and Kaernbach (2008) examined mean speech amplitude

and its variation as caused by different intended emotions of six student actors, namely, a neutral speaking style and the five basic emotions anger, fear, joy, sadness, and disgust, using three different methods. Root mean square amplitude, mean absolute amplitude, and amplitude envelope which were extracted framewise from each utterance in steps of 10ms and averaging 20% of the loudest frames, representing the mean of the loudest 20% of each utterance.

Mismatches of utterance linguistic emotion with prosodic emotion has been shown to be one of the contributing factors to change in emotion category of a speech signal. Natural and synthetic prosody modification of speech sound show that mismatching prosody and emotion category of speech causes emotion specific speech to sound neutral in Prasanna and Govind (2010, pp. 783-784). Prasanna and Govind (2010, pp. 783-784) attempts to perform emotion transformation by Prosody modification, they use the estimated excitation parameters which can be incorporated in prosody modification task to convert speech from the given emotion to the target emotion. The prosody modification used involves introducing the desired pitch contour characteristics and strength of excitation in the given emotion to obtain the target emotion. The method was also proposed in Murty et al. (2009) where they used the knowledge of accurately estimated epochs. The epochs are also estimated for prosody modification in Rao et al. (2007). The conversion of the given emotion to neutral is done by using excitation parameters namely, mean pitch, standard deviation pitch, and excitation strength derived from EEG and speech signal of one emotion category to recreate another emotion category of the same speech. In converting fear speech to neutral speech, the mean, standard deviation, and strength of excitation have to be scaled by the factors 0.71(1-0.29), 0.83(1-.17) and 1.22(1+0.22), respectively. The strength of excitation is introduced by scaling the Hilbert envelope of the LP residual as used in Prasanna and Yegnanarayana (2007) and accordingly modifying the residual prior to prosody modification. The modified strength of excitation and pitch contours for angry to neutral emotion conversion show that the mean and standard deviations of the pitch values have been scaled and are close to the neutral case. Similarly, the strength of excitation is also scaled and resampled so that they are relatively closer to the neutral. The researchers conclude by showing that informal listening to synthesized speech gave a feeling that the sounds sound more neutral than the given original emotion. The challenge with this method of prosody modification is that inaccuracy in the first activity of identification and detection of speech emotion acoustic features may lead to inaccuracy in

identification and detection of prosody modified emotional speeches or inaccuracy in emotional signification intentionality, since different emotions may trigger different intentions.

A reversion of the same activity by Prasanna and Govind, (2010, pp. 783-784) can be done by amplitude modulation of a speech signal. In Mencattini et al. (2014), amplitude modulation has been shown to be a key role in speech perception. Small changes in speech signal's amplitude can be identified using Zero crossing rate which is commonly used in speech enhancement and speech synthesis. The zero-crossing count can serve as an indicator of the frequency at which energy is concentrated in the signal spectrum. Zero Crossing Rate (ZCR) is also used as an algorithm in selecting the most appropriate vocal features that represent speech emotion. Barhoumi and Ayed (2023). This may be due to variation in strength of sound caused by emotion categories of speech. Also, the energy of a signal depends on the amplitude of the wave. If the amplitude of signal is large, then it becomes a loud signal. Koduru et al. (2020). The amplitude of the speech signal varying significantly over time is also useful in speech voicing detection since short-time energy formulation that captures amplitude changes is used in establishing a foundation for distinguishing voiced from unvoiced speech. Uddin et al. (2023). Also, short term energy and short term mean amplitude can be used in the field of emotion recognition since the arousal level of emotions is associated with the short-term speech energy. (Jain et al., 2018; Ingale & Chaudhari, 2012; Shen et al., 2011).

Emotion/emotive forces which have been identified by mean amplitude of a speech signal are one of pragmatic carriers of meaning in speech, their physiological and acoustic features are also acoustically detectable. Other physiological carriers of speech pragmatic meanings include physiological modifiers of speech attitudes, Excitation, Energy, Intonational phrasing, Prominence, Duration, and Loudness. Pragmatic, physiological, and acoustic carriers of meaning in speech which are acoustically detectable, serve to indicate the attitude of the speaker of an utterance.

On the other hand, speech meaning, and speech intentions are closely related to speaker's attitude, for example, a speech utterance with an apologizing intention aligns with an apology attitude rather than superiority, or sarcastic attitude. Since speech meanings and speech intentions cannot be directly detected from speech unless there is an additional listener judgment task, Correlation of evaluation of speech

meanings and intentions associated with speaker's attitude and evaluation of physiological features associated with speaker's attitude may indicate accuracy of the speech intention and speech meaning. For example, Correlating Speech intentions in their accurate spoken attitude and confirming presence of physiological features of an appropriate attitude may indicate an utterance is accurately intended as detected. Otherwise, when speech intentions are not spoken with their accurate attitude such as when an apologizing utterance is spoken with an ironic, sarcastic, or threatening attitude and fail to indicate detectable physiological features of their appropriate attitude, such as an apologizing attitude, then the utterance may indicate other intentions outside the utterance linguistic contents.

There are research works showing detectability of speaker's attitude (Vaissière, 2004; Fonagy, 1981; Hirschberg & Ward, 1992; Ward & Hirschberg, 1988; Bolinger, 1964; House, 2003; Ladd, 1996.), including, detectable agreeable emotions, disagreeable emotions, excitement, general excitement, tension (arousal), detachment, activeness, subordination, submission, non-threatening, desirous of the receiver's goodwill, politeness, lack of threat by the subject, more femininity, hesitation, uncertainty, surprise, incredulity, uncertainty, aggression, threatening, definitive, more authority etc., whose trends may simplify extra investigation in replicating acoustic data-based speech experiments using listener judgement task, instead, two experiments may be done, and their results correlated to directly detect data based speech emotional meanings and intentions without the aid of human raters. i.e., Phonetic experiment in two steps, first, correlating meanings and intentions with attitude, and then detecting acoustic manifestation of attitude. If both steps are successful, then acoustic manifestation of attitude may be useful in direct detection of speech meanings and intention using acoustic analysis tools from a raw spoken utterance.

A speaker's attitude refers to the speaker's predisposed state of mind that characterizes a person's expression toward a person, object, speech situation, or oneself. For example, Authority, Submission, Subordination, Apology, Abusive, Ironic, Sarcasm, Intimacy, Incredulity, Superiority, Inferiority, Threatening, Activeness, Excitement, Detachment, Agreeing, Disagreeing, etc., Each of the eight Ekman emotion categories falls in at least one of the listed speech attitudes. In this case, emotion categories of similar attitude may manifest almost similar physiological and acoustic features of speech sounds in case the utterance contents match an emotion category articulating it. Such as contempt and disgust, fear and sadness, and happiness and surprise, but only when there's no mismatch between utterance content

emotion and voice emotion i.e., when a sad sentence is spoken with a sad voice, or when an angry sentence is spoken with an angry voice. This is because mismatching voice emotion with utterance contents emotion may as well signal difference in speaker's attitude when compared to matched content-voice emotional utterance.

However, not all attitudes of speech are detectable in one physiological feature. Several researchers instead have tried involving the role of more than one physiological feature in detecting speech attitudes since some speech attitudes may have less manifestation in one physiological feature and more manifestation in another physiological feature. This may be because of the manner of speech production which favors some speech attitudes than others in each of the physiological features of speech sounds. (Vaissière, 2004)

Therefore, the difference behind signified utterance meanings, functions, and intentions may be in an emotive force influencing the utterance surface structure or words present in an utterance. This is because 'If only an emotive force of a human voice determined emotional meanings, functions, and intentions, then there wouldn't be opposite and different mean amplitude valence of the same emotional voice of a spoken utterance by one person in ten different utterances of different semantic and syntactic highlights' besides, it is also evident in survey responses where one utterance in one dialogue is shown to have different intentions by different English listeners. In other words, each articulation chunk may be carrying its amplitude weight or other acoustic excitation features, and the amplitude differences in the structure of an utterance when being spoken affects the mean of all other articulation chunks in a series in an utterance, which when spoken in different emotion categories may lead to variation in voice features as representatives of different meanings. Thus, the finding that 'Emotional meanings, functions, and intentions are carried in and determined by words, not only voice features' supports the Theoretical foundation laid in Chapter 3. about, 'Denotative, Trigger and Affective emotional signification', where words have the power to denote, affect and trigger fluctuations of a person's state of mind, affecting the voice and face at the same time enough to be read as signifying different meanings, functions, and intentions, and when the voice alone such as intonation, or the face alone pretend to signify such meanings it may imply unawareness of sound systems of words, articulation chunks or an utterance by users of a language which may be affecting their voice features and sometimes the face.

Studies on changes in pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions due to influences coming outside the surface structure of a sentence reveal prosodic influences such as intonation patterns to be one of contributing factors. Emotional signification functions as much as intonation does in changing utterance meanings which makes a speech of a specific emotion category distinctive of its own meaning making cues such as stress, pauses, energy, loudness, or levelled meaning making cues. A study on perceptual cues in non-verbal expressions of emotion by Sauter et al. (2010) provides evidence on differences in meaning making perceptual cues where, sadness speech, for instance, differs from angry speech by having more pauses and higher pitch while angry speech has low pitch.

What intonation and emotional signification have in common in the process of changing utterance meanings is the emphasis on focus points in an utterance which is done by levelling and creating meaning making perceptual cues such as stress, pauses, energy, or loudness (amplitude) at different intervals between utterance chunks. This is shown in previous studies on how intonation influences utterance meaning providing evidence on attempts for stress levelling between chunks, for instance, it has been found in English and Bulgarian languages in Stoyneshka et al. (2010) where prosody has been shown to influence syntactic processing by levelling pauses between two phrases of the same utterance making it be spoken as one chunk. Comparing such findings with the current study, they demonstrate intonation and emotional signification to be similarly playing roles over each other, whereby applying emotional signification to an utterance may change intonation pattern of an utterance and by applying intonation patterns to an utterance may change emotional signification of an utterance.

Previous studies on emotional categorization of intonation patterns tried to group intonation patterns categories into different emotion categories and came up with results reflecting attitudinal functions of intonation. (Fonagy & Magdics, 1963; Halliday 1970; O'Connor & Arnold, 1973; Juslin & Laukka 2003; Scherer, 2003). The challenge in empirical explanation that studies on emotional categorization of intonation patterns face is inconsistency in aligning categories of intonation patterns with specific emotion categories leading to intonation focus inconsistency in attitudinal functions which means it is erroneous to group emotion categories into intonation patterns because they have different functional foundation. For instance, Rodero (2011) on influences of pitch levels and contour type on creating emotions, assigned different emotions (joy, anxiety, sadness, and calmness) to pitch patterns (pitch levels and contour types)

to perform attitudinal functions by arousing emotion sensations and verify association of elements of intonation with emotion categories. The results turned out that intonation contour type is highly significant and constitute a variable determined as a final component for recognizing emotions but ‘the applied emotional utterance performing sensation arousal lacked consistence in intonation focus points used to perform such attitudinal functions.’ There are other studies challenging emotion specific intonation patterns with different reasons, for instance, Pakosz (1983) regards intonation patterns thought to be in specific emotion categories as a matter of mere coincidence in arousal levels between intonation and emotion categories. Scherer et al. (1984) and Ladd et al. (1985) point out that emotional modulation of intonation in communication is continuous but not bound to epochs as utterances, which imply interdependence between triggers and response expressions in a natural communication as investigated in this thesis. Frick (1985) challenges emotional specific intonation pattern with modality specificity basis noting out differences between utterance-based intonation contours and voice-based intonation contours with the reason that an emotion category of an utterance is determined by verbal contents of words, not intonation of a voice articulating an utterance. Also, Bänziger & Scherer (2005) challenge emotion specific intonation patterns with the reason that linguistic utterance-based tones and contours are not well suited to describe pitch contours as applied in natural emotional communication.

An alternative explanation is that, Intonation is not bound to a specific emotion category or emotive force, but the two can perform similar functions or opposite functions depending on an utterance’s constituents. This may be because of levelling or leaving pauses, pause intervals, stress, duration of a chunk, and focus on utterance constituents which are prone to influence of both vocal intonation patterns (voice modality) and emotivity of utterance words in the same utterance.

Also, the emotional signification of a specific emotion category is not necessarily bound to a particular focus on meaning making cues, an utterance may be conditioned with a particular emotion category but exhibits different intonation pattern focuses for one emotion category which also shares meaning making focus points with another emotion category. For instance, Pell (2000) on the influence of emotion and focus location on prosody in matched statement and questions, found fundamental frequency contour representing 12 distinct productions of a sentence ‘Barry took the sailboat’ by a proficient research participant. The findings show that neutral, sadness, happiness, and angry emotion categories were found

to be having three different intonation focuses, which are, no focus, initial focus, and final focus. Therefore, there may be mutual influence between intonation patterns and emotional signification.

This thesis opens an approach to the pragmatic study of English emotional utterances and utterances involving interplay and mismatches of utterances, facial expressions, and prosody. Major findings, the implications of the study, limitations of the study, and suggestions for further studies are explained below.

6.2 Major Findings.

The research has achieved to explain an approach to understanding pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of a facial expression, voice, and an utterance in interlocution. Three major findings have been achieved which are:

First is the mechanism of emotional signification in four phases i.e., Trigger, Sensation, Signification, and Expression, this mechanism gives the speaker the skills to condition and recognize conditioned meanings, functions, and intentions through an interplay and mismatches of an utterance, voice, and facial expressions.

Second is the aspects of emotional signification, which are, emotional signification as a semiotic process and emotional signification as a pragmatic act.

The third finding is an emotional signification error which is a conditioning error seen by the hearer failure to accurately interpret the function of a signified emotional expression/utterance because of it being presupposing or implying a signified function not yet mentioned such as a congratulation wish without the basic reason/trigger which intends to make the hearer regret of decision done unconsciously. This is because what is on the face (expression) must reflect what is sensed (sensation) from the causative emotional utterance (trigger). But contrary to that, to create meanings, functions, and intentions by conditioning (emotional signification-conditioning), the speaker's interplay of facial expression and an utterance does not reflect any sensed background trigger and thus the speaker is thought to be creating meaning different from the primary meaning and function that the surface structure would usually perform.

6.3 Implications of the Study.

The research has achieved to explain an approach to understanding pragmatic meanings, functions, and intentions present in an interplay and mismatches of facial expressions, voice, and utterance in interlocution. It is expected to impart pragmatic signification competence to the reader and guide sociolinguists and pragmatists viewing of an interplay and mismatches of utterance, facial expressions, and voice.

6.4 Limitations of the Study.

The research experiments were successfully designed and implemented. However, the use of semi-natural simulated audio-visual database of English emotional utterances is slightly far from reality. The first limitation is that there could not be a specific set of emotional expression intensity and degree for each emotion category, thus, making room for overemphasis and underemphasis, given speakers sociolinguistic and individual differences. Also, Given the influence of utterance semantic satiation where participants knowing what they were going to speak before they speak with emotional expressions, and which do not come from their own minds might have altered variability of intensity and degree of emotional expressions. The second limitation is that participants individual perception of the utterance topic might have altered variability in intensity and degree of neutral states of emotional utterance expressions.

6.5 Suggestions for Further Research.

The results of this research analysis on functions carried in emotional signification as compared to results on studies of influence of emotion on intonation patterns, and studies on functions of intonation patterns, indicate that there may be mutual influence between intonation patterns and emotional signification.

Therefore, it's my call that future studies may do the following, first, take the functioning of emotional signification as an insight to investigating empirical mutual functional influence between intonation and emotion signification, this is because, What makes intonation and emotional signification different from each other may be irregularity in functional results in the way they affect one another, that is, one type of intonation pattern such as a final fall when applied to change two different utterances to a specific one similar function, the same shared functional results of those two different utterances may not necessarily be sharing the same emotion category as well. Another hint is an investigation on whether one type of emotive force when applied to change two different utterances to specific shared function such as to command, to inform, to ridicule, to question, to request etc., the same shared functional result of those two different utterances may not necessarily be sharing the same intonation category as well. And whether it may still be the case that, an intonation category such as final fall and one of emotional signification emotive force categories may demonstrate similar change toward the same function in more than two different utterances making it look like intonation patterns are emotion specific.

The second suggestion that the researcher puts forward for future studies is that, In the methodology chapter in creation of English audio database, to minimize the influence of overemphasis and under emphasis to the intensity and degree of emotional utterances expressions, future studies should consult or collect data from natural audio-visual speech database where emotional utterances expressions are spoken unpreparedly and in time to get rid of overemphasis and underemphasis despite semiotic, cultural and sociolinguistic backgrounds of speakers. Also, collection of audio databases should be done in a natural continuous emotional communication.

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Theoretical Readings

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APPENDIX A

Learner's consent and Information form 1

ENGLISH - CHINESE PHONETICS RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS EXPERIMENT INSTRUCTIONS.

Experiment purpose: Examining Acoustics-physiognomy asymmetry in English and Chinese utterances manifested in eight emotional expressions for phonetics, semantics, and pragmatics analysis.

Researcher's task: Recording speakers' voices for further analysis.

Participants tasks: Speaking out each of the ten utterances in eight (08) emotional expressions namely, Neutral voicing as the baseline, Anger, Happiness, Sadness, Surprised, Fear, Disgust and Contempt.

Experiment location: School of psychology, Suiyuan Campus, Nanjing normal University.

Experiment duration: From 2nd August to 15th August 2022.

This research experiment has been approved by the college of foreign languages and culture at Nanjing normal university under the supervision of Professor Shi Guang.

Experiment sentences are grouped in two languages as follows.

English Sentences

1. I'm so happy to meet you! How are you doing?
2. Guess what we found in the garden! A pair of gloves, guns, and that stolen gold!
3. I'd like to have chocolates, mirinda and some banana again.
4. Why are you sitting here? It's cold outside! Get inside!
5. Of course, you are right, especially reading inspiring quotes
6. Who wouldn't have gone to school to fulfill their dreams?
7. Could you find out what's a point of surprising us with another plastic surgery?
8. I mean they were doing it correctly from the very beginning.
9. They were aware of the boring, hurting, and meaningless programs like that.

10. In nine hours of goodnight, he didn't hear the first disgusting top hazard to mankind.

APPENDIX B

Learner's consent and Information form 2

ENGLISH PHONETICS RESEARCH PARTICIPANTS EXPERIMENT INSTRUCTIONS.

Experiment purpose: Examining the relationship between English intonation and emotion categories.

Researcher's task: Recording speakers voices for further analysis.

Participants tasks: Speaking out each of the 5 utterances in different emotional expressions from the eight (08) emotions categories namely, Neutral emotional category, Anger, Happiness, Sadness, Surprised, Fear, Disgust and Contempt.

Experiment location: School of psychology, Suiyuan Campus, Nanjing normal University.

Experiment duration: From 2nd August to 15th August 2022.

This research experiment has been approved by the college of foreign languages and culture at Nanjing normal university under the supervision of Professor Shi Guang.

Experiment sentences are grouped in two languages as follows

English Sentences

1(a) Do you accept working here?

1(b) I do. (*Neutral emotional category, Sadness emotional category, Angry emotional category*)

2(a) John is coming again to see me.

2(b) If I were you, I'd leave him straight away. (*Neutral emotional category, Angry emotional category, Fear emotional category*)

3(a) Sophia will come to your shop today

3(b) She likes candies. (*Neutral emotional category, Disgust emotional category, Surprised emotional category*)

4(a) I'll be cooking with you today

4(b) Can you pass the salt. (*Neutral emotional category, Contempt emotional category*)

5(a) See you

5(b) I'll come for you tomorrow. (*Neutral emotional category, Angry emotional category*)

6(a) That is my gift. (*Surprised emotional category*)

7(a) I apologize for stepping on your foot (*Happiness emotional category, Neutral emotional category, Sadness emotional category*)

APPENDIX C

Research Survey

Instructions: The following is a Linguistics research survey intending to find out relationship between the human voice, emotion categories, and utterance meaning. Listen to short dialogues between two speakers on each question and select Intention of the second speaker from the four options after each question. Questions number 18 and 19 require you to select your profession category and age group.

Question 1

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To swear
- To surrender
- To give up
- To complain

Question 2

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To swear
- To surrender
- To give up
- To complain

Question 3

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To give up
- To complain
- To swear
- To surrender

Question 4

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To warn
- To advice
- To wish
- To suggest

Question 5

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To wish
- To warn
- To advice
- To suggest

Question 6

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To suggest
- To advice
- To wish
- To warn

Question 7

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To ask
- To suggest
- To inform
- To complain

Question 8

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To suggest
- To inform
- To ask
- To complain

Question 9

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To complain
- To ask
- To inform
- To suggest

Question 10

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To ask
- To beg
- To request
- To inform

Question 11

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To beg
- To request
- To ask
- To inform

Question 12

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To suggest
- To warn
- To threaten
- To promise

Question 13

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To promise
- To suggest
- To warn
- To threaten

Question 14

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To inform
- To beg
- To ask
- To thank

Question 15

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To inform
- To remind
- To ridicule
- To apologize

Question 16

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To remind
- To ridicule
- To apologize
- To inform

Question 17

What is THE INTENTION of the second speaker? (Audio).

- To ridicule
- To inform
- To apologize
- To remind

Question 18

What is your profession?

- Linguistics
- Psychology
- Other

Question 19

What is your age group?

- 15 - 20 years old
- 21 - 30 years old
- 31 - 40 years old
- 41 years old and above

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